

D2.2

Final Version of PATTERN New Curriculum

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Author(s)	Theodora Kavvadia (OpenAIRE) Andrea Giraldo Sevilla (LPI)
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Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Alessio Livio Spera	APRE
Francesca Foliti	APRE
Giacomo Consolini	UniSR
Chiara Saviane	SISSA
Gitte Kragh	AU
Michelle van den Berk	DANS

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CS	Citizen Science
CDD	Communication, Dissemination & Data
D&E	Dissemination and Exploitation
GNI	Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion
KSAV	Knowledge, skills, attitudes and values
LSA	Latent Semantic Analysis
LC1	Learning Cycle 1
LC2	Learning Cycle 2
MHL	Mental Health and Leadership
OA	Open Access
OAP	Open Access & Scholarly Publishing
OS	Open Science
PI	Principal Investigators
PIW	Participation, Inclusion and Well-being
REI	Research Ethics and Integrity
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SC	Science Communication

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Executive Summary

The final deliverable **D2.2 – Final Version of PATTERN's New Curriculum** documents how the project's training offer evolved from the initial needs analysis in **D1.1** into a mature, evidence-driven programme. D1.1 mapped existing Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation training and identified gaps and needs across the eight PATTERN transferable skills — Open Access, FAIR Research Data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender/Non-Discrimination & Inclusion, Dissemination & Exploitation of Results, Science Communication, and Mental Health & Leadership — providing the baseline for curriculum design. Based on this evidence, **Learning Cycle 1 (LC1)** tested initial modules through pilots and feedback loops via Train the Trainers sessions, revealing the need for stronger progression and cross-thematic integration. **Learning Cycle 2 (LC2)** addressed these gaps by consolidating modules into an integrated curriculum, aligning them with the ResearchComp framework and refining the content through evaluation results, co-creation with pilot institutions, and the introduction of self-paced and blended formats. By the end of LC2, the curriculum had become a coherent, modular and reusable framework that responds to the needs identified in D1.1 and the lessons learned from LC1.

Methodologically, the final curriculum introduces four structured learning paths— Participation, Inclusion & Wellbeing (23 lessons); Communication, Dissemination & Data (15); Research Ethics & Integrity (4); Open Access & Scholarly Publishing (2) — each sequenced to support learners from foundational knowledge to advanced practices. These paths are organised around learner personas, such as Researchers (R1–R4), Research Managers and careers beyond academia, ensuring that early-career researchers, established academics, research enablers and trainers can follow tailored trajectories within or beyond academia.

LC2 emphasises active and applied learning through case studies, project-based assignments and problem-based scenarios, alongside a **train-the-trainer** model that supports local adaptation and sustainability. The curriculum is delivered via a digital ecosystem combining **OpenPlato** for self-paced modules, the **Projects** platform for collaborative assignments and evaluation, and institutional partnerships for hybrid and in-person sessions. This ecosystem ensures that materials are FAIR-compliant, SCORM-enabled and integrated with evaluation and personalized certification delivery.

Overall, **D2.2** presents a concise yet versatile curriculum that is ready for deployment across diverse institutions and learner types. It moves beyond one-off training events by offering modular, interoperable courses that can be reused, adapted and combined according to local needs. The curriculum's focus on transferable skills and competencies promotes researcher growth, professional adaptability and alignment with European Open Science and RRI policies. By incorporating self-paced learning, synchronous workshops, blended bootcamps and cross-institutional collaboration, the programme offers flexible learning pathways that accommodate different preferences and time constraints. Through this approach, PATTERN provides a scalable training infrastructure that supports continuous capacity-building, fosters

community engagement and embeds open and responsible research practices into the European research ecosystem.

1 Introduction

D2.2 – Final version of PATTERN new curriculum presents the final consolidated version of the PATTERN curriculum, bringing together the materials, content, topics and pedagogical focus developed throughout the project. D2.2 is not a stand-alone output, but the final report documenting the evolution of the PATTERN curriculum within WP2, in close connection with the piloting, evaluation, and refinement work carried out in WP3.

The development of the curriculum followed a step-by-step process. It began with the evidence base established in *D1.1 – Report on the analysis of existing training¹ activities and quality assessment*, which mapped existing Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation training activities and identified gaps and opportunities for new learning provision. This initial analysis informed the selection and development of PATTERN's eight transferable skill areas: Open Access, FAIR Research Data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in Research, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, Science Communication, and Mental Health and Leadership.

Building on this evidence base, *D3.1 – First version of PATTERN training plans in Pilot Organizations²* translated the emerging WP2 curriculum into implementation plans for the pilot organisations. It defined how the first training modules would be tested through webinars, workshops, summer and winter schools, and other institutional formats. D3.1 also introduced the two-cycle implementation model: Learning Cycle 1 (LC1) from May 2024 to April 2025, focused on first implementation and feedback collection, and Learning Cycle 2 (LC2) from May 2025 to April 2026, focused on expansion, refinement and deeper institutional embedding.

The curriculum was then further structured and refined through the interaction between WP2 and WP3. WP2 developed the training modules, while WP3 tested them in real institutional contexts and generated feedback on learner engagement, formats, audiences and implementation needs. This iterative relationship became more mature in LC2, where pilot organisations acted not only as recipients of training materials but also as co-creators, adapting modules to local contexts and needs, integrating real-life cases, aligning with national Open Science policies, and embedding hybrid and blended delivery models.

Along this process, the role of *D2.3 – First version of the training platform and modules sustainability plan³* was to ensure that the curriculum would not remain limited to individual training events. D2.3 introduced the sustainability logic for the PATTERN digital ecosystem, including the PATTERN website, OpenPlato, the Projects platform,

¹ Lagido, C., Kragh, G., & Nielsen, K. (2024). D1.1 Report on the analysis of existing training activities and quality assessment (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640916>

² Kavvadia, T., & England, J. (2024). D3.1 First version of PATTERN training plans in Pilot Organizations (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093951>

³ Cherel, E., Haklay, M., Giraldo Sevilla, A., & Kavvadia, T. (2025). D2.3 First version of the training platform and modules sustainability plan (1.0). Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.15297040](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15297040)

and the integration of training materials into reusable and maintainable formats. It also clarified that course materials should remain accessible through OpenPlato, Projects and Zenodo, and that self-paced Train-the-Trainer modules would support reuse, adaptation and long-term uptake.⁴

Taken together, these preceding deliverables show the staged pathway through which the PATTERN curriculum was developed, tested and refined. D2.2 therefore consolidates the outcomes of this process, bringing together the evidence base from the mapping phase, the first curriculum structure, the two-learning-cycles pilot implementation experience, the evaluation-informed refinements⁵, and the sustainability provisions for digital access and reuse. The following table summarises this progression by linking the main project phases with the deliverables that informed the final curriculum. It clarifies how each stage contributed to the development of a coherent, modular and reusable curriculum framework for Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation transferable skills.

Table 1 - Mapping the PATTERN Curriculum Development Pathway across Project Phases

Project phase	Relevant deliverables	Contribution to curriculum development	Application for D2.2
Consolidation of knowledge and identification of training needs	D1.1 – Report on the analysis of existing training activities and quality assessment	This phase established the evidence base for the curriculum by mapping existing Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation training provision and identifying gaps, needs, and opportunities across the thematic areas addressed by PATTERN.	The findings informed the selection of the eight transferable skill areas and provided the rationale for developing new or adapted training content.
Initial curriculum design and training framework development	D2.1 – First version of PATTERN new curriculum	This phase translated the mapping results into the first structured curriculum framework, defining the initial thematic focus, learning logic and pedagogical orientation of the PATTERN training offer.	D2.1 provided the basis from which the final curriculum in D2.2 was further developed, expanded and refined.
Pilot planning and operationalisation of training activities	D3.1 – First version of PATTERN training plans in Pilot Organizations	This phase connected curriculum design with implementation by defining how the emerging training	It enabled the curriculum to be tested in practice through different formats, audiences

⁴ More details are offered via D2.4 Final version of the training platform and modules sustainability plan, to be submitted in parallel timing.

⁵ More references available via D 3.3 Evaluation of outcomes and refinement strategy, [10.5281/zenodo.15209490](https://zenodo.org/record/15209490), & D 3.4 Final evaluation and summary of training programs, [10.5281/zenodo.20612574](https://zenodo.org/record/20612574)

		modules would be piloted across participating organisations and delivery contexts.	and institutional settings.
Piloting, monitoring and evaluation-informed refinement	D3.2 – Final Version of PATTERN Training Plans in Pilot Organizations; D3.3 – Evaluation of outcomes and refinement strategy; D3.4 – Final evaluation and summary of training programs	This phase captured the implementation experience from the learning cycles and used evaluation results to refine training formats, content, audiences, delivery modes and institutional adaptation.	It ensured that the final curriculum reflects practical piloting experience, learner feedback and evidence-informed improvements.
Platform integration and sustainability planning	D2.3 – First version of the training platform and modules sustainability plan; D2.4 – Final version of the training platform and modules sustainability plan	This phase defined how training materials would be integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem, including OpenPlato, the Projects platform and open repositories, and how they would remain reusable, adaptable and maintainable.	It supports the long-term accessibility, reuse and sustainability of the curriculum beyond individual training events and beyond the project lifetime.
Final curriculum consolidation	D2.2 – Final version of PATTERN new curriculum	This phase brings together the outcomes of mapping, curriculum design, piloting, evaluation, refinement and sustainability planning into the final curriculum framework.	D2.2 presents the consolidated PATTERN curriculum as a coherent, modular and reusable framework for developing Open Science and RRI transferable skills.

1.1 Interconnecting Open Science (OS) and Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) Frameworks

Within the scope of the current deliverable, the connection between **Open Science (OS)** and **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** provides the basis of the curriculum. OS contributes principles such as openness, transparency, accessibility, reproducibility and reuse, while RRI broadens the framework by emphasising ethics, inclusiveness, gender equality, public engagement, societal relevance and responsibility. Together, these frameworks support the organisation of the curriculum across the eight PATTERN transferable skill areas: Open Access, FAIR RDM, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion, Dissemination and Exploitation, Science Communication, and Mental Health and Leadership. This integrated approach is aligned with the European Commission’s positioning of Open Science as a central element of European research policy and with UNESCO’s

Recommendation on Open Science, which frames open science as a means to make scientific knowledge more accessible, inclusive and beneficial for society.⁶

This connection is important in D2.2 because the final curriculum is not presented simply as a list of thematic courses, but as a structured training pathway for developing transferable research competences. The curriculum responds to the gaps identified in earlier PATTERN work by combining knowledge, skills, attitudes and values in ways that support both individual researcher development and institutional capacity building. In this sense, the PATTERN curriculum connects OS and RRI not only at the level of content, but also at the level of competence development.

This deliverable shows the interconnection between OS and RRI. PATTERN establishes a first overview of the learning paths that link the eight transferable skills, the modular structure of the curriculum, the use of self-paced and synchronous formats, the Train-the-Trainer approach, and the integration of OpenPlato and the Projects platform. The curriculum is designed to be reusable and adaptable across institutions, countries and learner profiles, while maintaining coherence around shared Open Science and RRI principles. In line with UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Educational Resources, this supports the development of openly accessible and adaptable training materials that can be adjusted and reused by trainers and institutions while preserving quality, openness and sustainability.⁵ Thus, D2.2 presents the final PATTERN curriculum as both a content framework and an implementation model for building long-term Open Science and RRI capacity.

⁶ UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO.
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949>

2 Methodological Approach

This Chapter presents the methodological foundations guiding the design, implementation, and evolution of the PATTERN training programme in Learning Cycle 2 (LC2).

During LC1, the methodological focus was placed on identifying training needs, testing preliminary modules, and validating pedagogical approaches across pilot organisations. While this phase successfully established a shared foundation for OS and Responsible RRI training, it also revealed important limitations. Training provision was often fragmented, progression between beginner and advanced levels was not always integrated, and connections across thematic areas remained limited. As a result, learning experiences were sometimes perceived as isolated rather than part of a coherent developmental pathway.

LC2 addresses these challenges through the introduction of a more mature and integrated methodological framework. Central to this evolution is the development of structured learning paths that are explicitly aligned with researcher personas (R1–R4) and career stages. These learning paths are grounded in competency-based design principles and informed by European frameworks such as ResearchComp and the EURAXESS Researcher Development Framework. This ensures that learning outcomes are clearly defined, transparent, and progressively developed across training activities.

At the same time, LC2 reinforces more pragmatic and practical approaches by a stronger emphasis on project-based and problem-based learning, enabling participants to apply knowledge in realistic scenarios. Furthermore, training activities are increasingly embedded within institutional structures, including doctoral programmes, research support services, and professional development frameworks, contributing to long-term sustainability and impact.

Within this methodological context, the Competency Mapping and Learning Paths, developed based on each module's training analysis and material play a central role, providing a shared foundation that supports all thematic areas and ensures coherence across the PATTERN curriculum.

A competency framework specifies a structured statement of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values (KSAV) a learning programme intends to develop, and describes the learning progression (also known as proficiency levels) and target group. The competency mapping is the analytic process that aligns learning outcomes, modules and assessment to framework elements, aligning KSAV with each module and lesson/course along with learning outcomes, in order to provide a constructive alignment (Biggs, 1996) and actionable assessment (auditable matrix). The curriculum is the result of organizing content, sequence and assessment, while the learning path connects all these elements with their targeted persona.

Traditionally, the learning paths (also known as learning trajectories or pathways) is an adaptive web-based system that describes a sequence of instructional materials

and activities suggested to a learner, adapted to their knowledge, preference, needs and goals (Brusilovsky, 2001; Brusilovsky & Peylo, 2003). Hence, the learning path in the adaptive learning field is the output of a sequencing and optimisation process rather than a fixed object and suits all targeted learners (Brusilovsky & Vassileva, 2003; Chen 2008).

In PATTERN, we link the “traditional” EdTech learning paths with a qualification, VET and lifelong learning policy perspective. Here, a learning pathway is an institutional or systemic route a person can take through and between education, training and recognition opportunities. It includes these horizontal and vertical permeabilities, as well as credit recognition opportunities or validation of semi-formal or informal learning, linking UNESCO’s flexible learning pathways and CEDEFOP’s permeability/progression routes. Here the object is a semi-directed structure of progression and portability that links algorithmic sequences, cognitive models and validation opportunities (Giraldo Sevilla, A. et al. 2026) as a response to Union of Skills and ERA Agenda policy needs.

2.1 Part A: Construction of Learning Paths

In competency based curriculum design, the learning path is the final and learner-centred element that links competency frameworks, competency mapping and the curriculum with the validation opportunities explained above and reference instruments, such as, in the case of PATTERN, ResearchComp, DigComp 3.0, RMComp and GreenComp and, methodologically, the Turing approach to competencies in higher education (Gonzalez & Wanegaar, 2003).

To create the PATTERN learning paths, a lexical and semantical computational analysis was done to link the 8 modules and 44 courses (both for cycle 1 and cycle 2) with European Competency Frameworks (ResearchComp, RM Comp, CitSci Comp V0 V0, DigComp 3.0 and GreenComp), as well as target personas (Researchers, Research Managers, Careers outside of Academia), based on EURAXES and the Open Studio results on this topic.

2.1.1 Learning paths: Similarity analysis method and pipeline

The analysis covers 44 lessons, part of PATTERN 8 modules, and 156 competences in the following competency frameworks: Research Comp (n=39), CitSci Comp V0 (n=34), RM Comp (n=50), DigComp (n=21) and GreenComp (n=12).

Each module and lesson is composed by the title of the module, summary as well as the KSAV and learning outcome descriptions extracted from the training presentations, guidelines and training analysis and added to the PATTERN Curriculum V2. The extraction used the same methodology.

The method captures both lexical and semantic similarity: a latent semantic analysis (LSA) layer was used to calculate and analyse the cosine similarity (lexical analysis) and a pre-trained BERT model for Competencies analysis was used to analyse semantic similarity. The pipeline design is bidirectional so quantitative outputs can be traced back to the qualitative source text for expert validation.

The specific calibration of this pipeline, the term-frequency scaling, the n-gram ranges, the latent space dimensionality and the weighting of the surface and meaning signals are licensed CC BY-NC-SA to allow building upon the author's work non-commercially, providing credit to the author and license the derivate works or new creations under identical terms.

2.1.2 Learning paths: visualization of results

As a result of this analysis, the learning paths are visualized in different ways: (1) a network graph where the connections among learning modules are shown and the suggestions by persona or cross-cutting topics could be filtered; (2) a landing page in the PATTERN webpage where the public can have access to the results from the analysis in an interactive way is currently under development, including the four structured learning paths, personas, modules mapping with existing competency frameworks and a headmap visualization with more information on the 8 modules affinity with existing competency frameworks.

⁷In LC2, this integration is further strengthened through the expansion of competency areas. New content on funder requirements, rights retention, dissemination and exploitation strategies, and inclusion and well-being is systematically embedded, responding to gaps identified in LC1 and aligning training with current European policy priorities and research practices.

The modular design allows learners to engage according to their needs and experience level, while blended delivery formats, combining self-paced modules on OpenPlato & PBL study cases in Projects platform, with in person and hybrid sessions that support broader participation, community building and adaptability across institutional contexts.

At the pedagogical level, LC2 places stronger emphasis on active and applied learning. Case studies based on relevant EU projects, real-world scenarios, and project-based activities are systematically integrated, enabling learners to apply competencies in practice.

Overall, PATTERN Learning Path for Open RRI strengthens the coherence and impact of the PATTERN curriculum by establishing a common competency baseline and supporting a structured, sustainable capacity-building model.

The only limitation is that this method captures distributional and ontological meaning. However, these results should go through a “human” transdisciplinary review process for validation to further work on how courses could be implemented in different cross-sectoral settings.

2.1.3 PATTERN Curriculum and competence mapping

To support this methodological alignment, the final curriculum defines a set of thematic design orientations across the eight PATTERN transferable skill areas and their related modules and 44 courses developed (see Annex I, Curriculum V2). The

⁷ More references available at Chaper 4

curriculum further describes not only the summary of the course, time or delivery method, but the KSAV, splitting Skills into *know how* and *practice*, along with learning outcomes from the course. These data were extracted from the powerpoint presentation, guidelines as well as external references used as source in PATTERN material.

Each module and lesson has been mapped (1) with each competency framework and each competency, to provide a better view on how the lessons are aligned with these frameworks, as well as (2) among them (more information in 2.2. Learning Paths).

In terms of convergence between lessons and competency frameworks, below we could observe the closest framework per lesson (Figure 1):

Figure 1 - Closest framework per lesson
(Source: own elaboration)

Taking each module strongest framework, CitSci Comp V0 (25 of 44 courses) and ResearchComp (11 above 44 courses) have the strongest convergence and overlap with PATTERN curriculum. RM Comp (7 above 44 modules) covers the management-oriented modules, including funder requirements, project oversight, equality-diversity-inclusion, research finance and leadership. Finally, DigComp covers the data related courses and GreenComp is more distant, as this was not a specific focus of the project.

Figure 2 - PATTERN Curriculum to Framework convergence
(Source: own elaboration)

When it comes to how densely the curriculum converges with each framework (overlaps and strong convergence zones), amounts might look small but, as we could observe, each module and course spanned several competences at once, so no single competence matches a whole module. Here, CitSci Comp V0 converges most densely with PATTERN curriculum (27.2% of pairs overlap or strong zone), followed by ResearchComp (10.6%) and RM Comp (8.8%). DigComp 3.0 (6.4%) sits low and GreenComp's apparently higher 14.2% comes entirely from diffuse mid-level overlap with no strong matches (0 of 528 pairs), so it reflects a broad but shallow, transversal link rather than genuine thematic convergence. Per pair scores might seem modest by design but taking into account that each module spans several competencies and no single module matches only one competency, these results are significant.

These orientations clarify how the shared competency logic of the Learning Paths is operationalised across the curriculum, while allowing each thematic area to retain its specific focus, learner profiles and delivery formats.

- **Research Integrity (RI)** integrates scenario-based ethics training, authorship dilemmas, misconduct prevention and supervision responsibilities within competency progression.
- **FAIR RDM** embeds practical data lifecycle exercises, Data Management Plan activities, metadata work, repository selection and real-case FAIR implementation tasks.

- **Open Access (OA)** connects publishing strategies with copyright, rights retention, trusted publishers, repository use and funder compliance requirements.
- **Science Communication (SC)** applied communication skills are useful for the interaction with different types of non-expert audience, focusing on media and policymakers.
- **Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E)** aligns learning activities with project-based outputs, impact pathways, intellectual property and Horizon Europe requirements.
- **Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion (GNI)** incorporates inclusive research design, bias-awareness practices, gender dimension in research, intersectionality and respectful research environments across modules.
- **Citizen Science (CS)** uses participatory case studies, stakeholder engagement scenarios, recruitment and community engagement exercises.
- **Mental Health and Leadership (MHL)** strengthens competencies related to well-being, team management, mentoring, inclusive leadership and sustainable research careers.

Figure 3 - Thematic Area to Competency Framework affinity.
(Source: own elaboration)

If we zoom in how thematic areas distribute across framework (thematic area framework affinity), Open Access and FAIR RDM are stronger connected with ResearchComp and CitSci Comp V0; Research Integrity towards ResearchComp and CitSci Comp V0; Citizen Science as well as Gender and Inclusion towards CitSci Comp V0; Mental Health & Leadership towards ResearchComp and RMComp. Finally, when it comes to Science Communication there is a tendency towards all frameworks with a higher extent to CitSci Comp, ResearchComp and RM Comp; and Dissemination and Exploitation as well, although affinity is higher with CitSci Comp and RM Comp.

Finally, in contrast to ResearchComp, CitSci Comp and RM Comp, both DigComp 3.0 and GreenComp remain cooler across every thematic area, never exceeding 0.33, which confirms that their connection to the curriculum is transversal rather than thematic. This is confirmed by the mean similarity per pair against convergence share (per framework) calculation (Figure 4, below):

Why the mean misleads: high mean does not imply high convergence

Figure 4 - Mean similarity per pair against convergence share, per framework. (Source: own elaboration)

The mean-versus-convergence comparison explains why this holds even for GreenComp, as it ranks second on convergence, but all of that breadth is shallow overlap with no strong matches: it touches many competences lightly, through transversal vocabulary rather than dedicated sustainability content. On the other hand, DigComp 3.0's average score is close to the others, yet its convergence is the lowest of the five. A high average therefore does not make a framework central; what matters is convergence depth, which is what separates a thematic anchor like CitSci Comp from a transversal connector like GreenComp.

2.2 Part B: Learning Paths Identified

To create the learning paths, we used all the evidence from the PATTERN curriculum and competency mapping expanding it to design structured paths that could help organizing the lessons in a way that could be helpful to our targeted personas as well as policy makers and future projects.

Two outputs are being created: the learning paths explorer, a web-based interactive tool that could link these visualizations and results with the active links of our courses; a connection network that draws the courses grouped by type of path and lets the user highlight by the paths by researcher career stage, research manager ladder and

beyond academia paths. Both outputs will provide a curated reading and a personalized visualization of paths according to interests.

All these outputs have been built on the calculations explained above along with complementary calculations that will be explained below. On the one hand, calculations that expand the lessons mapping and competency framework convergence with module-to-module convergence, lessons clustering to build the structured learning paths proposed, as well as statistical reliability check and validation of learning paths proposed.

On the other hand, there have been other layers added, such as the lesson-to-persona convergence, which has helped building the researcher career stage suggestions and the research manager ladder, as well as the paths for careers beyond academia. Finally, the connections or relations were parametered and the interactive curriculum network built.

2.2.1 Lessons to competency paths

This mapping makes it possible to link lessons with specific competencies and even learning levels from Competency Frameworks, which is an insightful evidence to link competencies to specific learning material.

This is the view for genuine coverage: Open Access aligns almost equally with CitSci Comp and ResearchComp, and FAIR research data management and Research Integrity each reach the overlap zone with all three research-facing frameworks.

Each module fans out into its lessons, and each lesson flows on to its closest framework, with ribbons coloured by module.

Figure 5 - Lesson to closest framework
(Source: own elaboration)

Gender and Inclusion (eleven lessons) and Science Communication (nine taking into account LC1 and LC2), flow overwhelmingly into CitSci Comp; Mental Health and Leadership flows almost entirely into ResearchComp; Research Integrity splits between ResearchComp and RM Comp. No module flows cleanly into one framework, which is the structural counterpart of the cross-framework overlap.

2.2.2 Lesson to lesson paths

All these calculations follow the same similarity analysis explained in 2.2.1. but expanding the lesson-to-lesson convergence with the same lexical, semantic and ontological method used throughout the analysis.

In terms of lesson-to-lesson convergence, with 44 lessons there are 946 possible pairings. The calculation flags a pairing whenever two lessons are clearly related, and almost half of them are as 461 of the 946 pairs (49 per cent) turn out to be related in content rather than sharing a few words by chance. In other words, the curriculum is tightly interwoven; most lessons have real kinship with many others. These 461 pairs had to be simplified as it would produce an unreadable tangle, so we first studied the relationships among the lessons through a similarity analysis (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Lesson-to-lesson convergence

Module-to-module convergence (mean lesson-to-lesson similarity)

Figure 7 - Module-to-module convergence

The lesson-to-lesson convergence (Figure 6) shows 196 connections in total, which is now legible while still capturing the degree of similarity. This evidence shows us as well how the lessons are connected. The figure 7, on the other hand, shows (outlined in green) the average similarity among the different lessons inside the modules so a high value means that the in-module lessons resemble one another. For instance, Mental Health and Leadership (0.52) and Dissemination and exploitation (0.51) are the most internally consistent modules, while Science Communication (0.33) is the most varied.

For information, in both figures each lesson's self-pair has been excluded as it would be redundant. Moreover, read together, the two figures above show us a better view of the path structure: the research-practice modules (Open Access, FAIR RDM, Research Integrity) sit close together, the people-centred modules (Gender and Inclusion, Mental Health and Leadership, Citizen Science) form a second neighbourhood, and the outward-facing modules (Science Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) form a third. Those three neighbourhoods are, in essence, the structured paths.

2.2.3 Building the structured paths from clustering

There have been 4 main clusters or “learning cores” identified among the 44 individual lessons. These four ontological cores (PIW, CDD, REI, OAP) are the clustering of the 44 lessons. The cores are competency-defined pathways rather than thematic “containers” in order to provide a cross-module learner-centred perspective.

Learning cores	Competency area characteristics	Modules involved	Lessons
Participation, Inclusion and Well-being (PIW)	Participation, inclusion, well-being and community engagement	CS, DE, GNI, ML, OA, RI, SC	23
Communication, Dissemination & Data (CDD)	Communication, dissemination, impact and data stewardship	FAIR RDM, GNI, OA, SC	15
Research Ethics & Integrity (REI)	Research ethics and integrity	FAIR RDM, RI	4
Open Access & Scholarly publishing (OAP)	Open access and scholarly publishing	OA	2

The cores are cross-modular based on the clustered information from all learning material provided rather than tags, topic labels or keywords in order to allow not just cross-modular connections but cross-lesson connections.

Below we could observe how each thematic module’s lessons are part of the learning cores (Figure 8):

Figure 8 - From thematic to ontological learning cores
Source: own elaboration

This lessons-to-lessons evidence how learning paths are not merely “editorial” or selected at hand. These learning paths are based on how each lesson (edge) is connected to the others. For instance, of the 196 edges, 149 (76%) are connected to one path and 47 (24%) crosses among paths. Moreover, the within path edges are also stronger on average (0.386) than the cross-path edges (0.361), while the strongest links are internal (141 of the 176) as expected, shown also intra-module coherence. In “network language”, the learning paths are genuine communities themselves and it shows how the structure the content designers reasoned is structured both at intra-modular and at cross-modular levels, showed by the clusters or connections among the learning modules.

2.2.4 Persona and career layers development

While the “learning cores” are the measured convergence at the lesson level through the ontological representation, rather than imposed by modules, the persona layer carries metadata that allows another perspective of the same curriculum (annex x).

Following the Project’s objectives, the Open Studio results and the comments from the EC Evaluator, three persona dimensions have been developed from established European references:

Figure 9 - Lesson-to-persona convergence and lesson relevance to careers beyond academia

A. Researcher career stage (EURAXESS R1 to R4)

Every lesson has been mapped following the EURAXESS researcher profiles, from R1 First Stage Researcher through R4 Learning Researcher, using the lessons stated proficiency levels and learning outcomes. As it could be observed, 39 lessons are relevant to R1, 42 to R2, 32 to R3 and 29 to R4. This mapping is what lets the network be filtered by a first-stage doctoral candidate.

B. Research Manager ladder

As suggested by the Project's second evaluation, Research Management has been considered with its own progression. Each lesson is additionally rated for its relevance to the RM Comp ladder, thanks to the lesson-to-competency mapping. 7 of the 44 lessons are of high research-management relevance and 26 of medium relevance, so the curriculum shows a partial research management perspective. High relevance has been assigned to lessons located in the strong convergency zones and medium relevance is where it is overlapped with other personas or career beyond academia in the framework analysis.

C. Careers beyond academia

The third persona dimension answers a question that researchers increasingly ask: where does this competence lead outside the university. This has been part of PATTERN's main challenges.

Here, each lesson is tagged with the EURAXESS beyond-academia sector it most prepares a researcher for, so the network can be filtered by intended destination as readily as by career stage.

Sectors are assigned per lesson through an EURAXESS-grounded competence-to-sector crosswalk. Each beyond-academia destination is given a profile drawn from the EURAXESS Researchers' Careers Beyond Academia toolkit, with ResearchComp as the transferable-competence basis and the TRACK (research and knowledge-transfer management) and MR2YR (entrepreneurship) projects informing those two profiles; each of the 156 competences is then scored for its affinity to each profile, and every lesson responds to a sector through the competences it builds rather than through its module. The resulting coverage, in lessons of 44, is industry & private-sector r&d (17), research management & knowledge transfer (15), science communication & media (14), science policy & public sector (13), entrepreneurship & innovation (11), third sector, ngos & civil society (10).

Most lessons prepare for more than one destination, which reflects the transversal value of research competences. The spread across industry, research management, science communication and policy is broad, while the third sector and entrepreneurship are the more specialised destinations a smaller set of lessons points to.

2.2.5 Interactive curriculum network and connections

This work is currently being finalized and deployed in the PATTERN website to provide an entry point to our material and waiting for a final quality assurance, reliability and validation process of the preliminary results showed above. Also, because it is our intent not to add only lessons and materials, also adding the practical case studies and scenarios part of each course as well as the train the trainers and self-paced training in Open Plato and Projects, which is currently mapped as part of WP2.2 Platform development and WP2.3 Sustainability. Still, up to date, the curriculum network renders the same 196-edge graph as a living map. Each lesson is a node whose size grows with the lesson's duration, and each retained similarity is an edge. The effect is that the four ontological cores reappear as visible clusters on the canvas without any cluster being hard-coded

The network is the dynamic, explorable counterpart of the static figures below, and it is where the multi-parameter filtering described next becomes useful.

Curriculum network grouped into thematic neighbourhoods

Each shaded region is one neighbourhood that a learning path follows; nodes are lessons (size by duration). Grey lines join lessons in the same neighbourhood, orange lines bridge neighbourhoods. The dense interiors and sparse bridges are why the paths hold together as distinct journeys.

Figure 10 - Static rendering of the curriculum network
Source: own elaboration

Figure 10 is a static image of the interactive network, grouping lessons into three thematic neighbourhoods. Each core is internally dense while the orange bridges between them are comparatively few (76 per cent of all connections stay inside a core), which is the visual form of the clustering result, holding together as a distinct competency pathway.

Curriculum network as an arc diagram: 44 lessons in a row, connections as arcs

Lessons are ordered along the axis by module (coloured band at the bottom). Each arc joins two related lessons; thicker arcs are the strongest links. Tall arcs that jump between modules are the cross-neighbourhood bridges.

Figure 11 - Curriculum network as an arc diagram
Source: own elaboration

Figure 11 shows another way to see the connections, where the lessons are laid out in a single row grouped by learning core, and every connection is an arc above the line. Dense fans of grey arcs sit over each core (its lessons reinforcing one another), while

the long orange arcs that leap across the row are the cross-core bridges. The eye can follow any single lesson's links without the crowding of a force-directed layout.

3 Cross-Cutting Methodological Principles Supporting Curriculum Implementation

The scope of the PATTERN curriculum is explicitly transversal: it equips researchers to apply Open Science and RRI principles across publishing, data stewardship, integrity, citizen engagement, inclusion, communication, impact, and sustainable leadership. As reflected in the accompanying curriculum matrix and in D2.1 Annex 2, each module is specified by transferable skill area, competence type, learning outcomes, delivery mode, tools, and assessment, allowing institutions to assemble coherent pathways rather than one-off sessions. Addressing Learning Path Challenges through Project- and Problem-Based Modular Design.

PATTERN addresses WPI finding that much existing provision is introductory and fragmented by structuring each thematic area into modular units that can be recombined into guided pathways. D3.1⁸ explicitly defines learning paths as combinations of self-paced courses, study cases, flipped classroom activities and project-based exercises, and the Open Access pathway demonstrates this through modules where learners draft Open Access sections and embed compliance directly into research project plans. This is consistent with the logic of problem-based learning, which strengthens transfer by situating learning in authentic and ill-structured problems.

3.1 Active Learning and Learner-Centered Approaches

Interactivity is treated as a design principle rather than an optional enhancement: PATTERN emphasises quizzes, peer exchange, reflective tasks, case work and contextual adaptation.⁹ A clear example is the FAIR RDM “Planning for FAIR”¹⁰ session, where learners create and review a basic Data Management Plan through case-based exercises and project work instead of receiving only conceptual input. This corresponds to the broader evidence base showing that active learning improves learner performance and reduces failure relative to lecture-only formats.

3.2 Train-the-Trainer Approach

Train-the-Trainer is PATTERN’s principal multiplier mechanism for scalability, enabling thematic leaders to transfer content, pedagogy and implementation guidance across pilot organisations while preserving room for local adaptation. D2.1 records formal TtT sessions in LC1 for FAIR RDM, Science Communication, Open Access and Research Integrity, while the FAIR RDM bootcamp further extended this logic by preparing data stewards to reuse PATTERN materials in their own institutions.

⁸ Kavvadia, T., & England, J. (2024). D3.1 First version of PATTERN training plans in Pilot Organizations (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093951>

⁹ Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., Mcdonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active Learning Increases Students’ Performance in Science, Engineering, and Mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111, 8410-8415.

<http://www.pnas.org/content/111/23/8410.full.pdf>

¹⁰ Part of the course : ” FAIR Research Data Management: A Practical Introduction”

In line with UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Educational Resources, the PATTERN methodology also emphasises the development of reusable, adaptable and openly accessible training materials. This supports the wider objective of building shared training capacity, enabling trainers and institutions to adapt learning resources to local contexts while preserving their quality and openness.¹¹

3.3 Digital Learning Ecosystem and Tools

Scalability is reinforced through a dual digital infrastructure: OpenPlato for self-paced, SCORM-compliant courses and the Projects platform for case-based and project-based learning. In LC2, this enabled, for example, self-paced Science Communication delivery alongside reusable Citizen Science study cases and exercises, while D3.2 identifies platform standardisation, localisation and tool integration as explicit design objectives. This approach is well aligned with UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Educational Resources, which promotes openly licensed, adaptable and reusable digital learning materials as a basis for equitable and sustainable learning ecosystems.

3.4 Learner Progression and Pathways

PATTERN organises progression through structured pathways that combine beginner, intermediate and advanced modules according to audience, institutional role and thematic need. D2.1 illustrates this with the Open Access onboarding path for early-career researchers and PhD learners, where introductory modules are followed by more applied modules on funder compliance and project integration; the same principle underpins broader progression across researcher stages. This is coherent with the European framework for research careers, which updates the R1–R4 profiles, Research Management ladders and careers outside academia, and supports competence development across successive research stages and career contexts.

Learner progression in PATTERN is not understood as a linear sequence that all learners must follow in the same way. Instead, it is organised through flexible pathways that combine transferable skill areas, learning levels, delivery formats and learner roles. This allows the curriculum to respond to different starting points: early-career researchers may begin with foundational modules or validate transferable skills in case they have extensive experience in other areas, while more experienced researchers, trainers, research managers or support staff may engage with applied, advanced or trainer-oriented resources or foundational modules if they would like to expand their knowledge, in a lifelong learning perspective.

The table below provides a representative mapping of how this progression is operationalised across the eight PATTERN transferable skill areas. It does not list the full curriculum catalogue; rather, it illustrates how selected modules function as entry points or progression anchors within each thematic area. The table shows how PATTERN combines thematic content with delivery formats and R1–R4 learner profiles, making visible the connection between curriculum structure, learner needs and implementation formats.

¹¹ UNESCO. (2019). *Recommendation on Open Educational Resources (OER)*. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373755>

The mapping also demonstrates the transversal character of the curriculum. Each thematic area contributes to a different dimension of Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation competence development, while the combination of self-paced courses, workshops, trainer guides, flipped classrooms, case-based activities and project-based exercises supports different forms of learner engagement. In this way, the table acts as a bridge between the methodological principles described above and the thematic area analysis presented in the following chapter.

Table 2 - Representative mapping of transferable skills

Transferable skill	Representative PATTERN resource / module	Main delivery and engagement format	Learner persona served and progression function
Open Access	Open Access Publishing: Overcoming Challenges and Busting Myths; Meeting Funder Requirements: Navigating Open Access Publishing; Empowering Researchers: Retaining Copyright and Maximising Impact; Trusted Publishers for My Research	Self-paced courses, Train-the-Trainer resources, workshop scenarios, practical activities and trainer guides	R1-R4 , with trainer/support reuse. R1 learners are introduced to OA principles and publishing models; R2-R3 learners apply this knowledge to funder compliance, rights retention, trusted publishing and publication decisions; R4 profiles, including librarians, science managers and trainers, use the intermediate and TtT materials to support funders, national and/or institutional open access policies.
FAIR RDM	FAIR Research Data Management: A Practical Introduction; Planning for FAIR: Introduction to RDM and DMPs; A Deeper Dive into Putting FAIR RDM into Practice; State-of-the-Art Training in FAIR RDM	Self-paced as well as classroom based beginner and intermediate courses, blended workshops, case-based DMP exercises, use cases and Train-the-Trainer materials	R1-R4 . R1 learners build basic FAIR RDM and DMP literacy; R2-R3 learners apply FAIR principles to metadata, repositories, licences, access and reuse; R4 profiles, including data stewards, librarians and trainers, use the intermediate and TtT materials to support institutional data stewardship.
Citizen Science	Co-design Workshop: Introduction to Citizen Science; Introducing Citizen Science; Participant Recruitment and Community Engagement; 10 Citizen Science case-study resources on the Projects platform;	Project-based resources, case studies, synchronous workshops, webinars and participatory exercises	R1-R3 , with potential trainer reuse. R1 learners gain introductory understanding of Citizen Science and participatory research; R2-R3 learners apply co-design, participant engagement and community involvement methods; trainers can adapt case studies and project-based

Transferable skill	Representative PATTERN resource / module	Main delivery and engagement format	Learner persona served and progression function
Research Integrity	Citizen Science & FAIR RDM		resources for local workshops.
	Research Integrity & Good Scientific Practice (GSP)	Self-paced course with five structured modules, quiz-based completion and reusable course description on the Projects platform	R1-R4. R1 learners acquire foundations in Good Scientific Practice, authorship and misconduct prevention; R2-R3 learners connect integrity principles to supervision, collaboration and responsible research environments; R4 profiles can use the course as a common institutional reference for integrity training.
Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion	Gender Equality and Inclusion in the Research Lifecycle; A Social-Cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias; Risks of Informal Relationships in the Workplace; Blocking Toxic Speech Online PBL Workshop: Master suppression techniques, Counter strategies and Confirmation techniques; Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Open Science, Education and Tech; Gender, Diversity and Inclusion in Planetary Health (3 sessions)	Self-paced course, webinar-supported delivery, presentations, reflective exercises and synchronous session materials	R1-R4. R1 learners develop awareness of gender equality, bias and inclusion; R2-R3 learners apply inclusive research design and bias-awareness practices in projects and teams; R4 profiles use the materials to support institutional inclusion, training delivery and culture change.
Science Communication	Introduction to Science Communication: Skills for Today's Researchers; Science Communication for Trainers: Tools and Guidelines for Delivery; Science news case-study exercises	SCORM/self-paced course, Train-the-Trainer guide, flipped classroom activities, practical communication exercises and case studies	R1-R3, with trainer reuse. R1 learners acquire basic science communication skills for non-expert audiences; R2-R3 learners apply media, policy and public communication strategies to their research; trainers use the guide, slides and exercises to deliver or adapt the course.
Mental Health and Leadership	Responsible Research Supervision; Thriving/Surviving as an International Postdoctoral	Project-based workshop modules, webinars, case-study exercises,	R1-R4. R1 learners are supported in wellbeing, career insecurity and navigating supervision; R2-R3 learners strengthen

Transferable skill	Representative PATTERN resource / module	Main delivery and engagement format	Learner persona served and progression function
Dissemination and Exploitation	Researcher; Researcher Mental Health: Advocating for Institutional and Policy Change; PhD Careers: Transferable Skills and Career Insecurity	reflective group activities and discussion-based formats	resilience, mentoring and leadership capacities; R4 profiles, including supervisors and research managers, engage with responsible supervision, institutional support and policy-oriented wellbeing practices.
	Get Funding for Your Research, then Disseminate, Communicate and Exploit the Research Results; Enhance Your Research Results, Unlock Their Full Potential for Tangible Changes and Benefits; project-based D&E exercises	Self-paced course, project-based exercises, Horizon Europe scenario work, synchronous or hybrid training delivery and applied resources	R2-R4 , with selected relevance for advanced R1 learners. R2-R3 researchers apply dissemination, communication, exploitation, IPR and impact planning to proposals and funded projects; R4 profiles, including research managers and support staff, use the materials to support project development, impact pathways and institutional training.

4 Thematic Area Analysis

4.1 OPEN ACCESS

Section	Curriculum Development
Overview and rationale	Open Access (OA) is a central component of Open Science and RRI. D1.1 defines OA as the effort to make academic information, including peer-reviewed publications and at least metadata, openly accessible. It highlights OA as an ethical requirement for publicly funded research and links it to evolving policy frameworks such as Plan S ¹² and funder mandates. The main challenges identified include differentiating OA routes, uneven implementation across disciplines and countries, copyright issues, rights retention, and compliance with funder requirements.
WPI: Evidence base and identified gaps	WPI mapped 34 Open Access resources, including 16 training resources and 18 non-course materials. ¹³ Most resources targeted beginner-level audiences and general OA awareness, while intermediate and advanced resources were limited. The mapping showed that OA, scholarly publishing and the publishing lifecycle were relatively well covered, but key practical areas remained underdeveloped. In particular, funder requirements, predatory publishing and rights retention strategies were identified as gaps requiring further development. These findings directly informed the design of new OA modules in PATTERN.
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and modules developed	LC1 focused on building foundational OA awareness and testing introductory training content. The main learning outcomes concerned understanding the value of OA, recognising publishing routes, identifying basic copyright and licensing issues, and reflecting on the role of OA in responsible and open research. The main personas were R1 early-career researchers, PhD candidates, researchers requiring basic orientation in OA, and research support staff. LC1 modules and pilot activities were delivered mainly through introductory online resources, pilot sessions and awareness-oriented formats.
LC1 lessons and identified gaps	The main lesson learned from LC1 was that OA training could not remain limited to advocacy or general awareness. Researchers needed concrete support for publishing decisions, funder mandates, rights retention, repositories and predatory publishing. This aligned with D1.1, where funder requirements, repositories and predatory publishing were among the least represented topics in the mapped resources.
LC2: Core modules and new additions	LC2 marked a clear progression from basic OA advocacy to applied OA decision-making. The main OA modules and additions included “Meeting funder requirements: navigating Open Access Publishing,” “Trusted publishers for my research: decoding good practices & overcoming predatory publishers,” and “Empowering researchers: retaining copyright and maximize your impact in Open Access Publishing.” These modules directly addressed LC1 and WPI gaps by focusing on funder mandates, Horizon Europe compliance, national requirements, predatory publishing, trusted journals, copyright and rights retention strategies. Training materials are accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,
LC2: Personas and reach	LC2 expanded the target audience from mainly introductory learner groups to a wider persona-based model. R1 learners were reached through doctoral seminars, summer schools and winter schools; R2–R3 researchers engaged

¹² [‘Plan S’ and ‘coalition S’ – Accelerating the transition to full and immediate Open Access to scientific publications](#)

¹³ *D1.1 Report on the analysis of existing training activities and quality assessment* (Version 2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640916>, pp. 35–36.

Section	Curriculum Development
	with rights retention, funder requirements and trusted publishing; and R4 learners, including librarians, research managers and senior researchers, were targeted through policy-oriented and Train-the-Trainer activities. LC2 update reports 16 piloted sessions, including self-paced, face-to-face and online activities, reaching around 300 participants across researchers, PhD students, Master students, librarians and postdoctoral researchers.
Learning formats and pedagogy	LC2 introduced a blended and practice-oriented pedagogical model. Formats included webinars, bootcamps, face-to-face sessions, self-paced SCORM courses, case-based exercises, checklists, group discussions and Train-the-Trainer activities. The LC2 approach combined asynchronous preparation with live interaction and applied decision-making. Learners worked with real publishing scenarios, funder compliance questions, journal evaluation exercises, rights retention strategies and repository-related decisions.
Integration with the digital ecosystem	OA modules were integrated into PATTERN's digital ecosystem through OpenPlato and the Projects platform. Materials included course/session resources, trainer guidance, session plans, presentations, exercises, assessments and introductory video tutorials. Training materials were prepared for OpenPlato and made available in at least six languages: English, Greek, Hungarian, Croatian, Portuguese and Turkish.
Synergies with other themes	OA is strongly connected to FAIR RDM, especially through repositories, metadata, open data, data sharing, licences and funder requirements. It also connects with Dissemination and Exploitation, since OA publishing, rights retention and open dissemination contribute to visibility, uptake and impact. Additional links exist with Research Integrity, particularly through responsible publishing, trusted publishers and avoidance of predatory publishing.
Lessons learned and future directions	The main LC2 lesson is that OA training is most effective when it is practical, policy-aligned and locally adaptable. Future development should continue to expand advanced OA training on rights retention, funder compliance, repository workflows, trusted publishing, research assessment and emerging EU policy requirements. The LC2 resources provide a strong basis for continued reuse through OpenPlato, national adaptation by pilot organisations, and possible future certification or Train-the-Trainer pathways around rights retention and OA compliance.

Open Access: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
Open Access publishing: overcoming challenges and busting myths available as self-paced course in Hungarian, Greek, Croatian, Portuguese and Turkish; also available as SCORM package on Zenodo.	Understanding OA principles; navigating publishing routes; evaluating OA options; applying Open Science publishing practices.	Learners can explain OA models, distinguish publication routes, identify benefits and challenges of OA, and make informed publishing decisions.
Meeting Funder Requirements: Navigating Open Access Publishing — Train-the-Trainer module on OpenPlato and Zenodo; includes guidelines, session plans, activity materials and participant evaluation resources for a 2-hour face-to-	Understanding funder requirements; interpreting OA mandates; applying compliance strategies; connecting OA to project/grant obligations.	Learners can identify OA requirements in funded projects, select compliant routes, understand embargoes/licences/repository obligations, and plan publication compliance.

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
face course or adapted webinar.		
Empowering Researchers: Retaining Copyright and Maximising Impact — Train-the-Trainer module on OpenPlato and Zenodo, including PPT presentations, practical activities/games and guidelines		Learners can recognise copyright and licensing implications, apply rights-retention strategies, and choose publishing practices that preserve reuse and maximise impact.
Trusted publishers for my research: decoding good practices and overcoming predatory publishing — Train-the-Trainer module on OpenPlato and Zenodo; includes PPT presentations, practical activities and guidelines.	Rights retention; copyright awareness; licence selection; impact-oriented publishing.	Learners can assess journal and publisher credibility, identify predatory indicators, use trusted-publisher criteria, and select appropriate venues for research outputs.
Quick start to Open Access — Greek Projects resource with module description, PPTs, docx materials and links to web resources. Project exercise in Hungarian for winter school. Portuguese PPT session resources on funder requirements and rights retention. Multilingual OpenPlato self-paced OA modules in Hungarian, Greek, Croatian, Portuguese and Turkish.	Journal/publisher evaluation; responsible publishing; critical assessment of publishing venues; avoiding predatory practices.	Trainers and support staff can adapt OA materials to national policies, institutional contexts and learner needs, while researchers can apply OA practices in their local funding and publishing environment.

4.2 FAIR RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

Section	Curriculum overview
Overview and rationale	FAIR Research Data Management (FAIR RDM) is a central pillar for strengthening Open Science and RRI practices. D1.1 presents FAIR RDM as an essential condition for reuse in a data-intensive research environment. Researchers need to manage, document, share and preserve data meticulously, in order to be able to deal with vast volumes of data, build upon prior work, and collaborate effectively.. The report also clarifies that “FAIR” is not synonymous to “open”: FAIR adheres to the motto ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ and focuses on combining responsible access decisions with rich metadata, persistent identifiers, standardized open protocols, and clear licences..
WPI: Evidence base and identified gaps	WPI mapped 31 resources identified for FAIR data as well as 31 resources for Research Data Management. Most resources were generic, English-language and aimed at beginner or general expertise levels. The mapping showed that introductory resources were relatively well represented, while advanced and practice-oriented materials were limited. D1.1 identified gaps in metadata standards, controlled vocabularies, file formats, interoperability, trustworthy repositories, persistent identifiers, long-term curation and advanced data stewardship.

Section Curriculum overview	
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and modules developed	<p>The first cycle established the initial structure for a five-session FAIR RDM modular suite, to be used in classroom based teaching, either online or in person. The first three sessions provided an introduction at beginner level; the following sessions provided more in depth understanding at intermediate level. Throughout the course, participants could work individually on exercises based on a selection of discipline specific research projects.</p> <p>The main learning outcomes included understanding FAIR principles, recognising the value of structured data management, developing basic Data Management Plan (DMP) skills, identifying appropriate repositories, and applying good practices for data documentation and reuse. The main personas were R1 early-career researchers, PhD students and researchers needing foundational RDM skills, with secondary relevance for librarians, data stewards and research support staff.</p>
LC1 lessons and identified gaps	<p>LC1 confirmed the importance of basic FAIR awareness, but also showed that the intermediate level materials were experienced as challenging by an R1 audience and that the curriculum would benefit if the modular approach was taken further to bespoke sessions for a dedicated audience. It also showed that learners needed opportunities to apply FAIR principles to concrete research workflows and standing work practices present in their own research environments rather than learning definitions and concepts. Examples are exercises with local tools and facilities, such local institutional repositories (eg. FULIR at RBI) or the ARGOS tool for writing a DMP.</p>
Adaptation/localisation between LC1 and LC2	<p>Between LC1 and LC2, the FAIR RDM materials were expanded and prepared for broader reuse. A major adaptation was the conversion of materials into two self-paced online modules made available through OpenPlato, that facilitate flipped classroom teaching: learners could familiarize themselves with the theory in their own time to prepare for a teaching session that laid focus on exercises with local tools.</p> <p>Localisation also took place across pilots: UMinho embedded FAIR RDM into doctoral seminars and its Open Data Winter School; RBI adapted FAIR RDM materials to the Croatian context; HEAL-Link translated FAIR RDM OpenPlato courses into Greek and split them into basic and intermediate levels; and UDebrecen and IZTECH produced national-level translated materials for OA and FAIR RDM.</p>
LC2: Core modules and new additions	<p>Core LC2 activities included the FAIR RDM & DMP webinar in June 2025, the FAIR RDM Bootcamp for Data Stewards in October 2025, and the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp in December 2025. The LC2 module suite included self-paced FAIR RDM content, DMP-focused workshops, metadata and PID exercises, repository evaluation, dataset curation workflows and advanced data stewardship topics.</p> <p>Training materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,</p>
LC2: Personas and reach	<p>LC2 expanded FAIR RDM training across several learner personas. R1 learners were reached through introductory modules, doctoral seminars, summer/winter schools and beginner-friendly webinars. R2–R3 learners engaged with applied FAIR RDM practices, DMP development, repository selection, metadata, PIDs and data reuse. R4 learners, including data stewards, librarians, repository managers, research data officers and research support staff, were targeted through bootcamps and Train-the-Trainer formats. The Data Stewards Bootcamp specifically targeted advanced RDM practitioners and experienced researchers, strengthening institutional data stewardship capacity.</p>
Learning formats and pedagogy	<p>LC2 used a blended and practice-oriented pedagogical model, combining self-paced SCORM modules, live online workshops, bootcamps, winter schools, face-to-face workshops, Train-the-Trainer sessions and hands-on</p>

Section	Curriculum overview
Integration with the digital ecosystem	<p>exercises. Though some FAIR RDM training continued in the setting of the 5 modules of LC1, other FAIR RDM workshops followed a flipped classroom model: teachers had the flexibility to choose a teaching model most suitable to their audience.. Pedagogically, the theme moved from awareness-raising to applied competence development, requiring learners to work with DMPs, repositories, metadata, PIDs, licences, dataset citation, data reuse and FAIR implementation decisions.</p> <p>FAIR RDM was strongly integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem. training materials were converted into SCORM-compliant e-learning modules and uploaded them to OpenPlato, enabling self-paced access, flipped classroom delivery and reuse across pilot organisations. The Projects platform complemented classroom based teaching by supporting applied case-based learning and practical exercises.</p>
Synergies with other themes	<p>FAIR RDM is closely linked to Open Access, particularly through repositories, metadata, licences, data sharing, funder requirements and the treatment of publications and datasets as interconnected research outputs. It also connects strongly with Research Integrity, since responsible data management supports transparency, reproducibility and accountability. FAIR RDM also links to Citizen Science, especially through community data stewardship, participatory data governance and CARE+FAIR approaches in citizen science and participatory research contexts. LC2 updates explicitly include inter-thematic work on Citizen Science, participatory research and CARE+FAIR Data Management.</p>
Lessons learned and future directions	<p>The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that FAIR RDM training must go beyond explaining FAIR principles and support learners in applying them in concrete research workflows. LC2 showed the value of self-paced preparation combined with applied live sessions, bootcamps, mentoring and Train-the-Trainer formats. Future work should continue strengthening intermediate and advanced FAIR RDM pathways, especially for data stewards, librarians, research support staff and senior researchers responsible for institutional data policies. Further development should focus on certification, continued localisation and translation, alignment with EOSC guidance, and deeper integration with Open Access, Research Integrity and Citizen Science.</p>

FAIR RDM: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
<p>FAIR Research Data Management: A Practical Introduction — OpenPlato self-paced beginner course, articulated in three sessions: 1) What is FAIR RDM and Why Does it Matter? 2) Planning for FAIR – Introduction to RDM and Data Management Plans 3) Putting FAIR into Practice. Zenodo session resources also include Session 1: FAIR Research Data Management – What is FAIR RDM and why should we do it?, Session 2: Planning for FAIR: Introduction to RDM and DMPs, and Session 3: Getting started with putting FAIR RDM into practice.</p>	<p>FAIR awareness; responsible data management; Open Science literacy; basic data stewardship.</p>	<p>Learners can explain FAIR principles, distinguish FAIR from open data, recognise the value of responsible RDM, and identify how FAIR practices support transparency, reuse and research quality.</p>

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
<p>Planning for FAIR: Introduction to RDM and DMPs — beginner session/resource; 8 project use cases related to the self-paced courses, each with five assignments: FAIRness of data, project DMP, project documentation, data repository, policy and practice.</p>	<p>DMP development; funder alignment; research planning; ARGOS/tool use; project-based application.</p>	<p>Learners can draft and review a basic DMP, connect data planning to funder and institutional requirements, use structured tools such as ARGOS, and apply FAIR decisions to real or simulated projects.</p>
<p>FAIR Research Data Management: A deeper dive into putting FAIR RDM into practice — OpenPlato intermediate self-paced course, articulated in two sessions: 4) Metadata, Knowledge Organisation Systems and Persistent Identifiers and 5) Repositories, Licences, Data Access and Data Citation. Zenodo resources include Session 4: A deeper dive into putting FAIR RDM into practice (Part I) and Session 5: A deeper dive into putting FAIR RDM into practice (Part II).</p>	<p>Metadata literacy; interoperability; persistent identifiers; repository selection; data citation.</p>	<p>Learners can apply metadata and PID concepts, evaluate knowledge organisation systems, select appropriate repositories, understand licences and access conditions, and support data citation and reuse.</p>
<p>State-of-the-Art Training in FAIR Research Data Management — OpenPlato Train-the-Trainer course consisting of five sessions, with lectures, real-world use cases and interactive activities. Zenodo posters include FAIR Research Data Management Training Materials Ready for Reuse and PATTERN From Co-creation to Competence: Innovative FAIR RDM Training for Enhanced Research Services.</p>	<p>Training facilitation; institutional RDM support; data stewardship; capacity building; reuse of OER-style materials.</p>	<p>Trainers and research support staff can reuse FAIR RDM modules, adapt materials to institutional contexts, guide researchers on DMPs and FAIR practices, and support institutional training provision.</p>
<p>Multilingual/adapted FAIR RDM resources from OpenPlato and Zenodo; project use cases; translated beginner/intermediate OpenPlato modules; local workshop materials and exercises.</p>	<p>Localisation; disciplinary adaptation; institutional embedding; multilingual training delivery; CARE+FAIR awareness.</p>	<p>Learners and trainers can apply FAIR RDM principles in national and institutional contexts, adapt examples and exercises to disciplinary needs, and connect FAIR data practices with Citizen Science, Open Access and responsible data governance.</p>

4.3 CITIZEN SCIENCE

Section	Curriculum Development
Overview and rationale	Citizen Science (CS) is an important component of the Open Science and RRI curriculum. It supports transparency, inclusivity, public engagement, and the democratisation of science. D1.1 highlighte that successful Citizen Science requires researchers to develop a broad skillset, including participatory methodologies, data management, communication, engagement, volunteer management and ethics.
WP1: Evidence base and identified gaps	WP1 built on previous work from EU-Citizen.Science and TIME4CS and identified 109 Citizen Science resources, making CS one of the most populated areas in the PATTERN mapping. The resources strongly covered introductory themes such as <i>Introduction to Citizen Science</i> , engagement, communication, best practices and Citizen Science PBL study cases. However, gaps remained in more specialised areas, including project sustainability, funding, institutional change, policy embedding, diversity and inclusion in participation, and the integration of local or traditional knowledge.
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/ competences, personas and modules developed	LC1 focused on exploratory training, early-stage pilots and testing potential use cases. Core Citizen Science concepts were introduced and it was tested how different learner groups responded to participatory research topics. The main learning outcomes focused on understanding Citizen Science principles, recognising the roles of citizens and stakeholders, reflecting on ethical and engagement challenges, and identifying applications of CS across disciplines. The main personas were undergraduate students, PhD students, early-career researchers and researchers interested in public engagement.
LC1 lessons and identified gaps	LC1 confirmed strong interest in Citizen Science but also showed that the first training offer needed greater pedagogical consolidation. Early case examples and discussions were useful, but they were not yet organised into a structured, reusable case library. LC1 also showed the need to move beyond general awareness and support researchers in designing, facilitating, evaluating and sustaining participatory research projects.
Adaptation/ localisation between LC1 and LC2	Between LC1 and LC2, the Citizen Science training offer was substantially consolidated. Early exploratory materials were transformed into a more complete modular package, including a workbook, slide decks, trainer guidance, learning outcomes per module, ethics prompts and facilitator documents. Case-based and project-based learning became central, with examples such as FoldIt, Isala, Rural Placenames, HARISSA and the Pisuna Program linked to learning outcomes, ethical dilemmas, stakeholder roles and data governance principles. Localisation was strengthened through Danish translations and Danish case studies.
LC2: Core modules and new additions	LC2 marked the transition from fragmented CS content to ready-to-use modular materials. LC2 activities included “Introducing Citizen Science: Fundamental Principles and Interactive Cases”, “Participant Recruitment and Community Engagement” and a full-day workshop, and a Train-the-Trainer course. The theme was expanded through inter-thematic work on Citizen Science, FAIR RDM, CARE principles and participatory research, including the development of CitSci Comp V0 for Researchers and Practitioners with the European Citizen Science Academy. Additionally, the “Introducing Citizen Science: Fundamental principles and interactive cases for trainers”, supports as a Trainer’s guide in the interactive, e-learning environment of OpenPlato. Training materials are accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository.
LC2: Personas and reach	LC2 broadened the target audience and delivery base. 20 LC2 training activities were reported, including Citizen Science workshops, webinars, summer school and related Science Communication activities, with 1267 registrations, 907 participants, 31 trainings (LC1 +LC2 results) 9. The main

Section	Curriculum Development
	<p>personas included Bachelor students, PhD students, postdoctoral researchers, researchers across several disciplines, and professionals outside academia. UHelsinki targeted Master students, PhD students, researchers, early-career researchers and research support staff, while TCD worked to embed Citizen Science into a compulsory online module for PhD students and taught Master's students.</p>
Learning formats and pedagogy	<p>LC2 used a broad mix of formats: in-person workshops, online webinars, case-based activities, project-based learning, workbooks, trainer guidance, slide decks, local case examples and Train-the-Trainer materials. Compared to LC1, pedagogy became more structured and reusable. Each case was connected to learning outcomes and adaptation guidance, allowing the same materials to be used across undergraduate teaching, PhD training, researcher workshops, online webinars and professional development settings.</p>
Integration with the digital ecosystem	<p>Citizen Science materials were integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem through the Projects platform and OpenPlato. Updated materials were made openly available through the Projects platform, while the Train-the-Trainer course was planned as an interactive guide in OpenPlato. The Projects platform plays a particularly important role because it hosts PBL cases, examples and practical exercises. LC2 updates report ten Citizen Science and two Science Communication PBL study cases/examples on the Projects platform, reused across multiple trainings.</p>
Synergies with other themes	<p>Citizen Science is strongly connected with FAIR RDM, especially through data quality, data governance, CARE+FAIR principles, community data stewardship and responsible reuse. It also links with Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion through inclusive participation, diversity of publics and power relations; with Science Communication through public dialogue and non-expert engagement; with D&E through public uptake and societal impact; and with Research Integrity through informed consent, ethical engagement, transparency and responsible data practices.</p>
Lessons learned and future directions	<p>The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that Citizen Science training requires more than introductory awareness. Researchers need practical support to design, facilitate and evaluate participatory research, including recruitment, engagement, ethics, data governance, communication and sustainability. LC2 demonstrated the value of localisation, institutional embedding and competency-based development. Future work should continue expanding multilingual versions, advanced co-creation modules, evaluation frameworks and guidance on long-term project sustainability, while strengthening links with FAIR/CARE data governance, inclusion and institutional policy.</p>

Citizen Science: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
The two modules, including case studies and a related workbook, are available in English and Danish on Zenodo, ready for reuse	Participatory research design; case-based analysis; ethical reflections; stakeholder analysis and engagement.	Learners can explain Citizen Science principles, analyse real CS cases, identify stakeholder roles and reflect on the ethical and practical dimensions of participatory research.
Participant Recruitment and Community Engagement — implemented as part of AU/UH LC2	Participant motivation and recruitment;	Learners can plan recruitment strategies, consider participant

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
open online and in-person workshops and linked to the CS learning offer.	sustained community engagement; communication; inclusive facilitation.	motivations, support collaboration and develop approaches for sustaining engagement in CS projects.
FAIR RDM in citizen science projects — identified in the resource mapping as one of the two CS Projects resources with stronger reusability potential. Additional LC2 inter-thematic materials include work on Citizen Science / Participatory Research and CARE+FAIR Data Management.	Data governance; FAIR/CARE awareness; responsible data collection; community data stewardship.	Learners can connect participatory research with responsible data practices, identify data governance issues in CS projects, and apply FAIR/CARE considerations to community-based research.
Citizen Science case-study resources on Projects platform — the CS Projects resources include case studies used for synchronous training. LC2 updates also refer to cases such as FoldIt, Isala, Rural Placenames, HARISSA and the Pisuna Program, linked to learning outcomes, ethical dilemmas, stakeholder roles and data governance principles.	Localisation; case-based analysis and adaptation; ethical considerations; application of the 10 CS principles to cases; interdisciplinary learning; contextual application.	Trainers and learners can analyse real Citizen Science cases and consider adaptation to their local context, disciplines and learner groups, while maintaining links to shared learning outcomes and ethical considerations. Identification of participants, motivations, engagement styles, and consideration of practical implementation of participatory research.
Train-the-Trainer Citizen Science course — available as an interactive guide in OpenPlato. Zenodo PDF mapping booklet: <i>Overview of learning opportunities: Citizen Science – PATTERN mapping of Open Responsible Research and Innovation training opportunities for researchers.</i>	Training facilitation; institutional embedding; curriculum reuse; community building.	Trainers and research support staff can reuse CS materials, facilitate interactive CS sessions, embed CS in doctoral or institutional training, and support sustainable communities of practice.
CitSci Comp V0 for Researchers and Practitioners — developed with the European Citizen Science Academy, including a glossary, seven competency areas, 33 competencies, competency levels from foundational to expert, sub-competencies, scenarios, tools and approaches.	Competence mapping; reflective practice; public engagement; stakeholder-oriented research.	Learners can position Citizen Science within Open Science and RRI, identify competence development needs, and connect participatory research to ethics, communication, data governance and societal impact.

4.4 SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

Section	Curriculum Overview
Overview and rationale	Science Communication plays a central role in strengthening the relationship between research, society, media and policy. Within PATTERN, SC is framed as a core RRI competence because it enables researchers to communicate not only research findings, but also methods,

Section	Curriculum Overview
	<p>implications, uncertainty and limitations. It supports researchers in engaging with non-scientific audiences, improving the visibility and relevance of their work, and contributing more effectively to public and policy dialogue.</p>
<p>WP1: Evidence base and identified gaps</p>	<p>WP1 provided the evidence base for the Science Communication curriculum. D1.1 identified 114 Science Communication training activities across Europe, including 99 training courses, workshops or e-learning modules and 15 non-course materials such as webinars, lectures and static resources. The mapping showed that most existing training was beginner-oriented and that several course-type activities had paid or restricted access. Existing resources covered science journalism, multimedia, social media, digital communication, science communication theory, media training, institutional communication, science policy, risk communication, health and environmental communication, and communication with policymakers. However, gaps remained around policymaker engagement, communication of uncertainty and limitations, AI communication, data visualisation, graphics, and diversity and inclusion in science communication.</p>
<p>LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and modules developed</p>	<p>LC1 focused on introducing researchers to the foundations of communicating with non-expert audiences. The main competences addressed included understanding the aims and models of science communication, adapting research content for different audiences, identifying key messages, understanding how media and policymakers operate, and reflecting on the role of researchers as experts in public and social contexts. The target personas were mainly PhD students, postdoctoral researchers and Master students with little experience in Science Communication. LC1 delivery relied primarily on live, interactive sessions, delivered in person or online</p>
<p>LC1 lessons and identified gaps</p>	<p>LC1 confirmed the need for practical Science Communication training, but also revealed the need for greater flexibility, asynchronous access, reusable trainer materials and a clearer modular structure. LC1 confirmed the need for Science Communication training, but also revealed the limited time availability of researchers and thus the need of a further selection of content with focus on practical skills and greater flexibility of training material and the need for asynchronous access by trainees.</p>
<p>Adaptation/localisation between LC1 and LC2</p>	<p>Between LC1 and LC2, the Science Communication offer was reorganised primarily in terms of delivery mode but also lightened up in terms of theoretical content to respond to the needs of the pilot institutions and the limited time availability of researchers. The module on social media was removed given the rapid pace of changes in the field. The other four modules were uploaded as material for trainers and used as the basis for developing an asynchronous course on OpenPlato, making the content usable in flipped classroom formats and independent learning pathways. Additional practical activities on the Projects platform were developed for trainers' led and asynchronous situations.</p> <p>As a result LC2 introduced both a trainers' guide on OpenPlato and a four-module self-paced course, making the content usable in flipped classroom formats and independent learning pathways. The trainers'</p>

Section	Curriculum Overview
<p>LC2: Core modules and new additions</p>	<p>guide includes module descriptions, learning objectives, time schedules, bibliographies, slides with notes and instructions for practical activities, allowing trainers to adapt the materials for live or flipped delivery.</p> <p>In LC2, Science Communication became a more structured and scalable learning offer. LC2 offered a trainers' guide, composed of four modules: . Module 01 – What is Science Communication; Module 02 – Writing for the media; Module 03 – Talking with the media; Module 04 – Communicating with policymakersThe course is designed for researchers with little or no prior experience in science communication. The first three modules provide foundational training, while the fourth module on policy engagement is slightly more advanced and builds on earlier skills related to communication with non-experts.</p> <p>Moreover, a self-paced course has been developed on the same four modules and two additional practical activities were developed as case studies accessible in trainer-led or asynchronous contexts.</p> <p>Trainers' materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository.</p>
<p>LC2: Personas and reach</p>	<p>LC2 targets researchers at different career stages, especially doctoral students, postdoctoral researchers and early-career researchers who need to communicate their work to wider audiences. The self-paced course supports learners with little experience and can be used in flipped classroom contexts too. Trainer's can find all materials need for frontal lectures and practical activities in the trainers' guide. Additional practical activities are available for all situations as case studies.</p>
<p>Learning formats and pedagogy</p>	<p>LC2 uses a blended and modular pedagogical model. Formats include self-paced SCORM modules, live sessions, trainer-led workshops, flipped classroom activities, group discussions and practical exercises. The pedagogy is strongly practice-oriented: learners reflect on their communication context, identify audiences, select messages, adapt written and verbal formats, and apply strategies for media and policy engagement. Compared to LC1, LC2 strengthens flexibility and depth because the curriculum can now be reused asynchronously, adapted by trainers and embedded in institutional training offers.</p>
<p>Integration with the digital ecosystem</p>	<p>Science Communication is integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem through OpenPlato and the Projects platform. The self-paced course is hosted on OpenPlato as SCORM-compliant content, enabling structured asynchronous learning and certification. The trainers' guide is also hosted on OpenPlato, providing reusable materials, slides, notes, time schedules and practical activity instructions. The Projects platform supports applied learning through PBL study cases and examples. All trainers' materials are also accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository.</p>
<p>Synergies with other themes</p>	<p>Science Communication is strongly connected with Dissemination and Exploitation, since both themes address visibility, audience engagement, impact, communication planning and the translation of research results into societal and policy relevance. It also connects with Citizen Science through public engagement and two-way communication with participants and communities; with Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion through inclusive communication and audience-sensitive</p>

Section	Curriculum Overview
Lessons learned and future directions	language; and with Research Integrity through transparency, accuracy, communication of uncertainty and avoidance of overclaiming.
	The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that Science Communication training must combine conceptual understanding with practical application. LC2 demonstrated that modular, reusable and self-paced formats increase accessibility and support broader uptake, while the trainers' guide allows institutions to organise live, interactive or flipped sessions according to their needs. Future development could include further elements on communicating uncertainty, the use of AI, data visualisation, and inclusive communication strategies. Further work should also deepen the connection between Science Communication and D&E, helping researchers link communication activities to policy influence, societal engagement and research impact.

Science Communication: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
Introduction to Science Communication: Skills for Today's Researchers — self-paced OpenPlato course. The course includes four modules: 1) What is Science Communication? 2) Writing for the Media 3) Talking with the Media 4) Communicating with Policymakers.	Audience awareness; message selection; adaptation of research content; communication strategy.	Learners have a deeper awareness of the relation between science and society and the role of science communication. They can better organise their communication, analysing the different audiences, selecting key messages and adapting research content to specific context and tools which are useful when dealing in particular with the media and policymakers.
Science Communication for Trainers: Tools and Guidelines for Delivery - OpenPlato Train-the-Trainer resource. It includes trainer guidelines, PPT presentations for lectures and practical activities, notes, schedules and bibliography for the four SC modules.	Training facilitation; modular course delivery; adaptation of learning materials; trainer reuse.	Trainers can organise Science Communication sessions, adapt materials to local contexts, guide group activities and support learners through practical communication exercises.
Module 2-3: Writing for and talking with the media	Media logic; news values; writing formats; message selection; verbal and non-verbal communication	Learners can understand the logic of media and when science can become interesting news. They can understand the different formats used by the media, how to select their content, how to prepare for interviews and strengthen their communication.
Science News Release Analysis – Workshop — Projects platform case-study exercise.	Media literacy; science writing; critical analysis of communication outputs.	Learners can analyse science news releases, identify strengths and weaknesses in media-oriented communication, and reflect

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
		on how research findings are translated for public audiences.
Writing Science News Headline and Lead Paragraph — Projects platform case-study exercise.	Writing for non-expert audiences; headline writing; clarity; accessibility; concise communication.	Learners can draft accessible headlines and lead paragraphs, simplify complex research content and communicate key findings in a clear and engaging way.
Module 4: Communicating with Policymakers within Introduction to Science Communication: Skills for Today's Researchers. This module is slightly more advanced and builds on the earlier modules.	Policy communication; stakeholder engagement; strategic framing; communication for impact.	Learners can understand the logic of policymaking, adapt messages for policy audiences and connect communication choices to broader research visibility and impact goals.
Full SC learning package: self-paced course, Train-the-Trainer guide, and Projects-based case studies.	Cross-thematic communication; public engagement; dissemination support; learner-centred delivery.	Learners and trainers can connect Science Communication with D&E, Citizen Science, Research Integrity and inclusion by applying communication practices to real research, public engagement and impact contexts.

4.5 GENDER, NON-DISCRIMINATION AND INCLUSION IN RESEARCH

Section Overview and rationale	Curriculum Overview
	Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in Research (GNI) is a key dimension of Open and Responsible Research and Innovation. It is framed through an intersectional approach, recognising that gender intersects with ethnicity, race, migration background, social class, wealth, gender identity, sexual orientation, neurodiversity and disability. The theme addresses both research content and research environments, including Gender Equality Plans, diversity strategies, non-discrimination measures and inclusive institutional change.
WPI: Evidence base and identified gaps	WPI identified a broad set of resources related to gender equality, diversity, intersectionality and inclusion. Most available materials were static resources or webinars, often useful for awareness-raising and guidance, especially around Gender Equality Plans, but less suitable for structured reuse or adaptation. The strongest content areas were Gender Equality, Diversity, Gender Dimension in Research, Gender Equality Plans, Gender Sensitive Research, Inclusion and Intersectionality. Gaps remained in inclusion beyond GEPs, gender-based violence, advanced materials for trainers and lecturers, and stronger qualification/certification models.
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and	LC1 focused mainly on introducing core concepts of gender equality, bias, non-discrimination and inclusion in research environments. Learning outcomes centred on recognising gender bias and stereotypes, understanding the relevance of gender equality in research and professional settings, exploring how to effectively block toxic speech, identifying structural barriers, and reflecting on individual and institutional responsibilities for inclusion. The main personas included early-career researchers, Master and PhD students, researchers, academic staff and

Curriculum Overview	
Section modules developed LC1 lessons and identified gaps	<p>research support staff. Training formats included seminars, workshops, and online resources.</p> <p>LC1 confirmed the relevance of GNI as a core PATTERN theme, but also showed that the training offer needed to move beyond awareness-raising. Learners required more applied tools, stronger links to the research lifecycle, and clearer integration with institutional practices. The LC1 offer was still relatively fragmented and needed a more coherent pathway connecting gender bias, research methodology, inclusion and workplace culture.</p>
Adaptation/localisation between LC1 and LC2	<p>Between LC1 and LC2, the GNI offer was methodologically strengthened. LC2 moved from general awareness and standalone sessions towards a more coherent set of modules addressing gender bias, toxic speech, gender dimension in research, workplace culture, informal relationships, inclusion and the research lifecycle. An asynchronous online GNI course for OpenPlato was developed, structured into three modules, and lesson's content was revised based on LC1 feedback, including duration reduction and more targeted topic selection. The theme was expanded through new sessions on the integration of the Gender Dimension in Biomedical Research Projects, Gender, Diversity and Inclusion in Planetary Health Research, including Global North and Global South epistemologies, CARE+FAIR data management in citizen science and participatory research, and inclusive Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning.</p>
LC2: Core modules and new additions	<p>LC2 introduced a more structured and applied GNI curriculum. The self-paced course "Gender Equality and Inclusion in the Research Lifecycle" was developed for beginners and intermediates participant and it includes structured content, real-life examples, interactive activities and a final quiz requiring 80% for certification. The course is structured into three modules. The first, A Social-Cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias, explores the cognitive mechanisms underlying gender bias, including social categorization, stereotyping, and confirmation bias. The second, Risks of Informal Relationships in the Workplace, applies this understanding to professional settings, providing practical tools to promote respectful and inclusive interactions. The final module, Integrating the Gender Dimension in Biomedical Research Projects, focuses on incorporating sex and gender as scientific variables throughout the research lifecycle, from study design to dissemination, using examples from basic and clinical research. Training materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,</p>
LC2: Personas and reach	<p>LC2 broadened the GNI audience across learner profiles. The self-paced course was designed for beginners and intermediate participants, while webinars and seminars reached Master students, PhD students, researchers, early-career researchers and research support staff.</p>
Learning formats and pedagogy	<p>LC2 uses a combination of self-paced learning, seminars, webinars, hybrid workshops, reflective activities, real-life examples and case-based learning. The pedagogical model operates at three levels: conceptual awareness of gender equality, stereotypes and inclusion; methodological integration of sex and gender analysis into research design, data collection, analysis, reporting and impact; and institutional/interpersonal practice, including informal workplace dynamics, inclusive communication and organisational policies. Compared to LC1, GNI is no longer treated only as an awareness topic, but as a methodological, ethical and institutional competence.</p>
Integration with the digital ecosystem	<p>GNI materials were integrated into PATTERN's digital ecosystem through OpenPlato and related course spaces. An asynchronous online course was developed to allow learners to complete content independently and receive a certificate after passing the final quiz. OpenPlato supports scalability, reuse and integration into institutional training offers. Some GNI modules, such as "A Social-Cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias" and "Gender</p>

Section	Curriculum Overview
Synergies with other themes	<p>Medicine,” were already part of UniSR’s PhD training offer, with further discussions around accreditation of gender-dimension training.</p> <p>GNI is strongly cross-thematic. It connects with Research Integrity through fairness, avoidance of bias, inclusive research environments and ethical treatment of participants. It links with FAIR RDM through data justice, sex- and gender-disaggregated data and inclusive data collection. It connects with Citizen Science through inclusive participation, power relations and community engagement. It also links with Science Communication through inclusive and audience-sensitive communication, with D&E through gender-sensitive impact pathways, and with Mental Health and Leadership through respectful workplaces, supervision, informal dynamics and institutional responsibility for wellbeing.</p>
Lessons learned and future directions	<p>The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that GNI training must move beyond general awareness and provide practical tools for research design, institutional practice and everyday research culture. LC2 demonstrated the value of applied modules addressing bias, methodology, workplace relationships and institutional change. Future development should strengthen advanced and trainer-oriented materials on gender dimension in research funding, monitoring and evaluation of GEPs, gender-based violence, inclusive research design, intersectionality and institutional change. Further work should also support certification, accreditation and integration into doctoral and researcher development programmes.</p>

Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in Research: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
<p>Gender Equality and Inclusion in the Research Lifecycle — OpenPlato self-paced course for beginners, articulated in three sections:</p> <p>1) A Social-Cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias 2) Risks of Informal Relationships in the Workplace 3) Integrating the Gender Dimension in Biomedical Research Projects</p>	<p>Gender equality literacy; inclusion awareness; reflective practice; responsible research culture.</p>	<p>Learners can explain core concepts of gender equality and inclusion, recognise forms of inequality and bias, develop concrete tools to promote respectful and inclusive interactions and identify individual and explores effective strategies for embedding sex and gender as scientific variables throughout the entire research lifecycle</p>
<p>A Social-cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias — UniSR PDF/presentation resource on Projects / Zenodo, based on synchronous session material.</p>	<p>Bias awareness; stereotype recognition; critical reflection; inclusive decision-making.</p>	<p>Learners can identify social-cognitive mechanisms behind gender bias, recognise how stereotypes shape evaluation and behaviour, and reflect on bias mitigation in research and professional settings.</p>
<p>Risks of Informal Relationships in the Workplace — UniSR PDF/presentation resource on Projects / Zenodo.</p>	<p>Workplace awareness; respectful communication; team culture; prevention of exclusionary behaviour.</p>	<p>Learners can recognise risks linked to informal workplace practices, identify how unconscious bias can emerge in everyday interactions, and apply respectful communication strategies.</p>
<p>Blocking Toxic Speech Online — UniSR s, co-</p>	<p>Digital inclusion; online communication; harm</p>	<p>Learners can recognise toxic speech and exclusionary online behaviour, reflect on digital</p>

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
designed with LPI and UHelsinki.	prevention; responsible engagement.	participation risks, and apply strategies for safer and more inclusive communication spaces.
Integrating the Gender Dimension in Biomedical Research Projects — UniSR PDF/presentation resource on Projects / Zenodo.	Critical thinking, data analysis, research design, interdisciplinary collaboration, ethical research practice, scientific communication	Learners can integrate sex and gender dimensions throughout the biomedical research process; analyze and interpret sex- and gender-sensitive data; identify and reduce research bias; communicate and apply findings to improve scientific quality and health outcomes
The Schools Challenge 24–25 – Diversity in STEM: Bias Challenges in AI — LPI project resource with information, instructions and resources to conduct an exercise.	Bias in AI; diversity in STEM; inclusive learning design; interdisciplinary reflection.	Learners can analyse bias in technological and STEM contexts, reflect on diversity challenges, and apply inclusive approaches to research, education and evaluation settings.
Combined LC2 GNI package: OpenPlato self-paced course + UniSR Projects presentations + LPI bias/diversity exercise.	Curriculum integration; cross-thematic learning; institutional adaptation; trainer reuse.	Learners and trainers can connect GNI principles to research design, communication, data practices, workplace culture and institutional change, supporting progression from awareness to applied inclusive practice.

4.6 DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Section Overview and rationale	Curriculum Overview
WP1: Evidence base and identified gaps	Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (D&E) supports the transition from knowledge production to knowledge use. It helps researchers communicate, share, apply and transform research outputs into scientific, societal, economic and policy impact. In the PATTERN curriculum, D&E is positioned as a practical competence area that enables researchers to connect project design, communication, stakeholder engagement, exploitation planning and impact generation.
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and modules developed	WP1 identified 21 training resources and 14 non-course materials related to Dissemination and Exploitation. Existing resources were stronger on dissemination-related skills, such as scientific and technical writing, multimedia, presentation tools and public speaking. Exploitation-related areas were less consistently covered, although intellectual property, copyright and business planning appeared in several resources. Gaps were identified in market analysis, proof-of-concept experiments, team creation, industry collaboration, regulatory affairs and social impact.
	LC1 focused on introducing researchers to the basic concepts and distinctions between communication, dissemination and exploitation. Learning outcomes centred on understanding the purpose of D&E, recognising the role of communication and dissemination plans, identifying suitable channels and audiences, and becoming aware of intellectual property, visibility and stakeholder engagement. The main personas were PhD students, early-career researchers, postdoctoral researchers and researchers involved in EU-funded or collaborative projects.

Section Curriculum Overview	
LC1 lessons and identified gaps	LC1 confirmed the relevance of D&E as a transferable skill area but showed that the training needed to become more coherent, applied and connected to the full project lifecycle. The first cycle demonstrated that D&E training should not remain limited to general communication advice, but should guide learners from proposal preparation and funding strategy to communication, dissemination and exploitation actions during project implementation.
Adaptation/localisation between LC1 and LC2	Between LC1 and LC2, the D&E offer was strengthened by connecting it more explicitly to Horizon Europe impact logic, funding requirements, project visibility, intellectual property and exploitation strategies. The self-paced course “Get Funding for your Research, then Disseminate, Communicate and Exploit the Research Results” became the central curriculum component. It links proposal development with communication, dissemination and exploitation practices, guiding learners from CDE definitions to the development of a Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) and practical examples of D&E activities.
LC2: Core modules and new additions	In LC2, the D&E curriculum became more structured, impact-oriented and aligned with Horizon Europe. The self-paced course is organised into four main lessons: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation in Horizon Europe; Managing Communication and Dissemination activities in Horizon Europe projects; Exploitation of scientific results and IPR; and Creating Actionable Knowledge: how to visually pitch your research results. The course is modular, allowing learners to complete all lessons or select specific blocks according to their needs. Training materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,
LC2: Personas and reach	LC2 D&E training is relevant for researchers and innovators who need to develop or contribute to collaborative R&I project proposals, especially under Horizon Europe Pillar II, and for those involved in communication and dissemination during project implementation. It addresses PhD students, early-career researchers, postdoctoral researchers, project staff, research support offices and researchers involved in EU-funded projects.
Learning formats and pedagogy	The LC2 D&E offer uses a modular and applied pedagogical model. The self-paced course supports independent learning through structured content, formative quizzes and final assessment, while practical and project-based exercises help learners apply concepts to real or simulated research projects. Learners work on CDE strategies, audiences, messages, channels, stakeholder needs, IPR, exploitation routes and impact pathways. Compared to LC1, LC2 moves from basic awareness to operational skills such as drafting CDE plans, managing dissemination activities, identifying exploitation opportunities and visually pitching research outputs.
Integration with the digital ecosystem	D&E is integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem through OpenPlato and broader PATTERN training platforms. The self-paced course supports asynchronous learning, certification and reuse. The Foundational Learning Path places Research Dissemination and Impact as an advanced integration phase, structured around Get Funding for Your Research and Disseminate, Communicate and Exploit Research Results. This positions D&E as a culminating competence area connecting proposal development, funding strategy, communication, exploitation and impact planning.
Synergies with other themes	D&E is strongly connected with Science Communication, since both address audiences, messages, visibility and the relationship between research and society. It also connects with Open Access, because publication strategies, rights retention and open dissemination influence reach and reuse; with FAIR RDM, because data sharing, repositories and metadata support visibility and impact; and with Research Integrity, because responsible dissemination requires transparency, accuracy and

Section	Curriculum Overview
Lessons learned and future directions	ethical handling of results. It also links with Citizen Science and GNI when dissemination plans need to address diverse stakeholders, inclusive communication, public engagement and equitable impact.
	The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that D&E training must be practical, project-based and connected to real funding and implementation contexts. LC2 strengthened the theme through Horizon Europe requirements, CDEP development, IPR, project visibility and exploitation planning. Future development should strengthen exploitation-oriented content, especially market analysis, proof-of-concept development, regulatory pathways, industry collaboration, business models and social impact assessment. It should also deepen links with Science Communication, Open Access and FAIR RDM so that impact is understood as a strategic process embedded from proposal design to project completion.

Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
Get Funding for your Research, then Disseminate, Communicate and Exploit the Research Results — self-paced OpenPlato course and central LC2 curriculum component for D&E.	Proposal literacy; project lifecycle awareness; impact planning; communication and dissemination strategy.	Learners can distinguish communication, dissemination and exploitation, understand their role in Horizon Europe projects, and connect D&E planning to proposal development and project implementation.
Lesson 1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation in Horizon Europe and Lesson 2: Managing Communication and Dissemination activities in Horizon Europe projects.	Communication planning; audience mapping; channel selection; project visibility.	Learners can identify target audiences, define messages and channels, plan communication and dissemination activities, and understand how these actions contribute to visibility and uptake.
Lesson 3: Exploitation of scientific results and IPR.	IPR awareness; exploitation planning; stakeholder thinking; use of results.	Learners can identify exploitation potential, recognise basic IPR issues, consider routes for making research results usable, and connect exploitation to scientific, societal, economic or policy impact.
Lesson 4: Creating Actionable Knowledge: how to visually pitch your research results.	Visual communication; actionable knowledge; pitching research; impact communication.	Learners can translate research results into accessible formats, prepare visual or pitch-style outputs, and communicate the value of research results to different stakeholder groups.
Full D&E course package: Get Funding for your Research, then Disseminate, Communicate and Exploit the Research Results, including modules on Horizon Europe, CDE planning, IPR and visual pitching.	Funding alignment; Horizon Europe impact logic; strategic planning; project-based application.	Learners can connect D&E actions to Horizon Europe expectations, draft elements of a Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, and align research outputs with expected impact pathways.

4.7 RESEARCH INTEGRITY

Section Overview and rationale	Curriculum Overview
	<p>Research Integrity (RI) is a core dimension of responsible, trustworthy and high-quality research. It supports researchers in understanding and applying ethical principles, professional standards and Good Scientific Practice (GSP). In the PATTERN curriculum, RI is positioned not only as a compliance topic, but as a foundational competence for building responsible research environments and strengthening trust in science.</p>
WP1: Evidence base and identified gaps	<p>WP1/D1.1 provided the evidence base for the RI curriculum by mapping a broad and diverse field of Research Integrity training resources. Existing RI resources covered responsible research and Good Scientific Practice, data practices and management, supervision and mentoring, research misconduct, informed consent and governance. The mapping also identified gaps in areas where RI intersects with intellectual property, research collaborations, privacy and confidentiality, Open Science practices, vulnerable participants, and power dynamics in research environments. WP1 further highlighted interactive resources such as the Dilemma Game, Moral Compass / VIRT2UE and The Embassy of Good Science as useful models, because they support reflective, case-based and dilemma-based learning.</p>
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and modules developed	<p>LC1 focused on introducing researchers to the principles of responsible conduct, Good Scientific Practice, authorship, misconduct prevention and ethical reflection. Learning outcomes centred on understanding core principles of research integrity, recognising questionable research practices and misconduct, reflecting on responsible authorship and publication practices, and understanding the role of supervision, mentoring and responsible research environments. The main personas were PhD students, early-career researchers, researchers, supervisors and research administrators.</p>
LC1 lessons and identified gaps	<p>LC1 confirmed that RI should not be delivered only as a compliance-oriented topic. Learners needed opportunities to discuss dilemmas, apply ethical principles to real - world cases/project based study cases, research situations, and reflect on their own roles in creating trustworthy research cultures. This highlighted the need for a more structured, modular and applied RI learning offer in LC2.</p>
Adaptation/localisation between LC1 and LC2	<p>Between LC1 and LC2, the RI offer was strengthened through the development of a structured self-paced course: "Research Integrity & Good Scientific Practice (GSP)." The LC2 version organises RI content into five modules: Good Scientific Practice: Authorship; Good Scientific Practice and Misconduct; Introduction to Research Integrity and the Virtue-based Approach; How to Foster a Responsible Research Environment; and Supervision and Mentoring. This structure responds to WP1 gaps by integrating misconduct prevention, authorship guidelines, mentoring responsibilities, virtue-based reflection and responsible research environments into one coherent course.</p>
LC2: Core modules and new additions	<p>In LC2, RI became more clearly positioned as a foundational and cross-cutting competence. The self-paced course "Research Integrity & Good Scientific Practice (GSP)" is designed for researchers and academic staff with basic familiarity with the research process. It is relevant for PhD students, researchers, supervisors, research managers, and includes a final quiz requiring at least 80% for certification. Each of the five modules lasts approximately 25 minutes and covers authorship responsibilities, ethical publishing, peer review dilemmas, misconduct</p>

Section	Curriculum Overview
LC2: Personas and reach	<p>such as fabrication, falsification and plagiarism, virtue-based ethics, responsible research environments, supervision and mentoring.</p> <p>LC2 addresses several learner personas. R1 learners, especially PhD students, benefit from foundational training on GSP, authorship and misconduct prevention. R2–R3 researchers engage with supervision, mentoring, responsible collaboration and ethical decision-making in more complex research contexts. R4 learners, including supervisors, administrators and senior researchers, are supported in fostering responsible research environments and embedding integrity principles into institutional practice.</p> <p>Training materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,</p>
Learning formats and pedagogy	<p>The LC2 RI offer combines self-paced learning, modular content, quizzes, case-based reflection and in-person workshops. The self-paced course provides structure and independent progression, while the final quiz supports assessable learning and certification. Pedagogically, the course combines conceptual grounding with applied reflection, asking learners to consider misconduct, authorship dilemmas, supervision responsibilities and responsible research environments. Compared to LC1, LC2 makes RI more structured, assessable and reusable, while maintaining space for experiential and dilemma-based learning.</p>
Integration with the digital ecosystem	<p>Research Integrity is integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem through OpenPlato as a self-paced course. The modular structure, quiz-based completion and certificate of completion support scalable delivery and reuse across institutions. The course also aligns with the broader LC2 strategy of packaging PATTERN materials as SCORM-compliant e-learning units, integrating them into OpenPlato, and supporting blended and interactive learning formats. Training materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,</p>
Synergies with other themes	<p>RI is strongly connected with several PATTERN thematic areas. It links with FAIR RDM through responsible data management, documentation, transparency and reproducibility. It connects with Open Access through ethical publishing, authorship, peer review, predatory publishing and publication practices. It links with GNI through fairness, inclusion, power dynamics and non-discriminatory research environments. It also connects with Citizen Science through informed consent, ethical engagement and responsible data governance, and with Mental Health and Leadership through supervision, mentoring, research culture, pressure and supportive research environments.</p>
Lessons learned and future directions	<p>The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that RI training needs to combine clear foundational knowledge with applied ethical reflection. LC2 showed that RI should not be treated only as compliance, but as a cultural and institutional competence. Future development should strengthen advanced RI modules on conflicts of interest, research collaboration, intellectual property, privacy and confidentiality, research evaluation reform, AI-related integrity challenges, and power dynamics in supervision and collaboration. More case banks and dilemma-based activities would also support trainers in adapting RI training across disciplines and institutional contexts.</p>

Research Integrity: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules	Transferable skills	Competences
Research Integrity & Good Scientific Practice (GSP) — self-paced course structured as the central LC2 RI learning resource.	Ethical awareness; responsible conduct; reflective practice; research culture.	Learners can explain core principles of Research Integrity and Good Scientific Practice and recognise their relevance across research activities.
Module 1: Good Scientific Practice – Authorship.	Responsible authorship; publication ethics; peer review awareness.	Learners can identify authorship responsibilities, recognise ethical publishing practices and reflect on peer review dilemmas.
Module 2: Good Scientific Practice and Misconduct.	Misconduct awareness; prevention of QRPs; ethical decision-making.	Learners can distinguish Good Scientific Practice, questionable research practices and misconduct, including fabrication, falsification and plagiarism.
Module 3: Introduction to Research Integrity and the Virtue-based Approach.	Ethical reflection; virtue-based reasoning; integrity-oriented judgement.	Learners can reflect on research integrity as a set of values and practices, not only as compliance with rules.
Module 4: How to Foster a Responsible Research Environment.	Research culture; institutional responsibility; collaborative practice.	Learners can identify conditions that support responsible research environments and recognise their own role in fostering trustworthy research cultures.
Module 5: Supervision and Mentoring.	Supervision; mentoring; leadership; prevention of harmful practices.	Learners can understand supervision and mentoring responsibilities and apply good practices that help prevent misconduct and support responsible research development.
Full RI package: Research Integrity & Good Scientific Practice (GSP), including five modules and final quiz requiring at least 80% for certification.	Self-paced learning; institutional reuse; assessable competence development; trainer adaptation.	Learners can progress from foundational RI concepts to applied reflection on authorship, misconduct, research environments, supervision and mentoring.

4.8 MENTAL HEALTH AND LEADERSHIP

Section Overview and rationale	Curriculum Overview
WP1: Evidence base and identified gaps	<p>Mental Health and Leadership (MHL) addresses the human, organisational and cultural conditions that enable researchers to work sustainably and responsibly. Initially mapped under Management and Leadership in D1.1, the theme highlights the importance of leadership, team development, self-organisation, conflict resolution, inclusion, career development and the ability to cope with pressure. In the PATTERN curriculum, MHL is positioned as a transversal competence area supporting both individual researcher wellbeing and healthier research environments.</p> <p>WP1 identified 44 Management and Leadership resources from 33 institutions, including 36 training activities and 11 non-course materials. These covered online, blended and in-person formats, but many were restricted or paid access. Existing resources covered leadership, project</p>

Section	Curriculum Overview
	management, team development, self-organisation, empowerment, strategic thinking and coping with pressure. Key gaps were identified around mentor-mentee relationships and networking, both directly linked to career development and mental health.
LC1: Learning outcomes, skills/competences, personas and modules developed	LC1 focused on establishing the initial scope of MHL and testing how mental health, leadership and researcher wellbeing could be addressed within the PATTERN curriculum. The first version of the training focused on the individual, institutional and systemic levels of mental health leadership, including choosing and managing a PhD supervisor, breaking the silence around wellbeing at work, and enabling institutional change. The main personas included early-career academics, PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers, supervisors, senior academics and administrative staff.
LC1 lessons and identified gaps	LC1 confirmed that MHL should not be treated as an isolated “support” topic, but as a transversal competence area linked to research culture, supervision, mentoring and institutional responsibility. It also showed the need for more dynamic, adaptable and practice-based materials that combine leadership, mental health, mentoring and networking for different researcher groups and institutional actors. Training materials will be accessible under FAIR principles in the Zenodo repository,
Adaptation/localisation between LC1 and LC2	Between LC1 and LC2, the MHL offer was significantly strengthened. modular training series was developed, tailored especially to early-career researchers and focused on emotional resilience, leadership development, mentor-mentee relationships and academic networking. LC2 also introduced stronger use of participant-submitted scenarios and real-life cases to stimulate reflective and problem-based learning. This created a feedback loop between delivery, learner experience and continuous content refinement.
LC2: Core modules and new additions	In LC2, Mental Health and Leadership became a more visible and active part of the PATTERN training ecosystem. LC2 activities focused on researcher wellbeing, leadership, career development and research culture. A major output was the PhD Wellbeing Festival, involving 7 trainers and 6 trainings on managing multiple identities within and beyond academia, boosting resilience, managing imposter feelings, building a wellbeing culture in academia, career planning and work-life balance. The LC2 portfolio also includes courses on Responsible Research Supervision, international postdoctoral experience, researcher mental health advocacy, research manager feedback on wellbeing support, and PhD career insecurity.
LC2: Personas and reach	LC2 expanded the MHL audience across career stages and institutional roles. 24 training activities were reported, including workshops and webinars, several international public events, approximately 580 participants out of 700 targeted, and a main audience of PhD students, postdoctoral researchers, researchers and research managers across multiple disciplines. Delivery included 9 online workshops/webinars and 15 in-person workshops and training sessions.
Learning formats and pedagogy	LC2 uses workshops, webinars, festivals, mentoring clinics, peer learning, case-based activities and problem-based learning. The pedagogy is experiential and participatory, recognising that mental health and leadership cannot be taught only through conceptual content. The learning progression moves from individual awareness and self-care to leadership, mentoring, institutional advocacy and policy change. Participant-submitted scenarios and real-life cases make the training more relevant to researchers’ lived experiences.

Section	Curriculum Overview
Integration with the digital ecosystem	MHL is integrated into the PATTERN digital ecosystem through OpenPlato and the Projects platform. The Mental Health Leadership training adopts a flipped classroom approach, with recorded sessions shared as Open Educational Resources through OpenPlato and the PATTERN platform. The Projects platform supports reflective and case-based learning by linking participant-submitted scenarios to sub-projects, enabling peer reflection and collaborative discussion around leadership dilemmas, academic isolation, team communication and mental health-sensitive research environments. OpenPlato hosts the “Mental Wellbeing in Academia: The Role of Research Managers_Trainer’s Guide”.
Synergies with other themes	Training Materials have been uploaded into Zenodo as well. MHL connects strongly with Research Integrity through responsible supervision, mentoring, research culture, power dynamics and prevention of harmful academic behaviours. It links with GNI through inclusive leadership, psychological safety and respectful workplace cultures. It also connects with Science Communication and D&E, since leadership involves responsible communication, team management and supporting researchers in public-facing or impact-oriented roles. It links with Citizen Science through community relationships and emotional labour, and indirectly with FAIR RDM and Open Access, as sustainable research cultures are needed to implement Open Science without overburdening individuals.
Lessons learned and future directions	The main lesson from LC1 to LC2 is that mental health and leadership training must be embedded in the broader research culture, not treated as an optional wellbeing add-on. LC2 showed the value of peer exchange, real-life scenarios, mentoring clinics, workshops and festivals. Future development should strengthen modules on supervision, academic career insecurity, inclusive leadership, conflict navigation, mentoring, work-life balance and institutional mental health policy. Further Train-the-Trainer resources should support research managers, supervisors and senior researchers as multipliers within their institutions.

Mental Health and Leadership: Curriculum Overview

LC2 training modules / available materials from resource mapping	Transferable skills	Competences
Mental Health Leadership modular training series — LC2 training package focused on researcher wellbeing, leadership, career development and research culture.	Researcher wellbeing; leadership awareness; research culture; institutional responsibility.	Learners can recognise mental health and leadership as part of responsible research culture and identify how individual, team and institutional practices affect researcher wellbeing.
Responsible Research Supervision — Projects platform course/resource.	Supervision; mentoring; responsible leadership; power-awareness.	Learners can identify responsible supervision practices, reflect on mentor-mentee dynamics and recognise how supervision affects wellbeing, integrity and research culture.
Thriving/Surviving as an International Postdoctoral Researcher and PhD Careers: How to Build Transferable	Career resilience; networking; self-management; transferable skills.	Learners can reflect on career insecurity, identify transferable skills, develop strategies for navigating

Skills & Address Career Insecurity — Projects platform resources.		postdoctoral or PhD transitions and build support networks.
PhD Wellbeing Festival training resources — six training topics: managing multiple identities within and beyond academia, boosting resilience, managing imposter feelings, building a wellbeing culture in academia, career planning and work-life balance.	Resilience; self-awareness; work-life balance; wellbeing strategies.	Learners can recognise common wellbeing challenges in research careers, apply resilience strategies, reflect on imposter feelings and develop healthier work practices.
Researcher Mental Health: Advocating for Institutional and Policy Change and A Feedback Workshop for Research Managers on Mental Wellbeing Support in European Institutions — Projects platform resources.	Advocacy; policy awareness; institutional change; research management.	Learners and institutional actors can identify structural drivers of poor wellbeing, propose institutional support measures and connect mental health to research management and policy change.
Scenario-based and case-clinic materials linked to MHL workshops and Projects platform sub-projects.	Reflective practice; problem-based learning; peer learning; conflict navigation.	Learners can analyse real-life leadership and wellbeing scenarios, discuss possible responses and apply supportive strategies in teams and institutions.

5 Conclusions

D2.2 presents the final consolidated version of the PATTERN curriculum, bringing together the outcomes of curriculum design, piloting, evaluation-informed refinement and sustainability planning. The curriculum covers eight thematic areas: Open Access, FAIR Research Data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in Research, Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results, Science Communication, and Mental Health and Leadership. Together, these areas provide a comprehensive framework for strengthening Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation competences across research communities.

The final curriculum responds to the gaps identified during the mapping and pilot phases by moving beyond introductory awareness-raising towards more advanced, interactive and context-sensitive training. Across the thematic areas, LC2 strengthened the practical orientation of the training offer through case-based learning, project-based activities, self-paced courses, trainer guides, workshops, webinars, flipped classroom formats and locally adapted materials. This evolution reflects the wider methodological shift of PATTERN from separate thematic modules towards a more coherent, modular and competence-based curriculum. The scope of the curriculum is therefore not limited to individual training resources. It provides a flexible, learner-centred framework that can support different learner profiles, from early-career researchers and PhD candidates to postdoctoral researchers, senior researchers, research managers, librarians, data stewards, trainers and institutional support staff. The learning paths introduced in the curriculum help organise this progression by connecting beginner, intermediate and advanced learning opportunities with transferable skills, researcher roles and institutional needs.

In addition, a central feature of the final curriculum is the organisation of training into structured learning paths. These learning paths connect the eight thematic areas with transferable competences, learner personas and different research career contexts. They support flexible progression for researchers at different stages, from early-career researchers and PhD candidates to postdoctoral researchers, senior researchers, research managers, trainers, librarians, data stewards and research support staff. The curriculum is therefore not limited to a catalogue of individual resources; it provides a learner-centred framework that can be adapted to different levels of experience, institutional needs and professional trajectories within and beyond academia.

Finally, a key achievement of the final curriculum is its integration into the PATTERN digital learning ecosystem. OpenPlato supports self-paced and SCORM-based learning, certification and reusable course structures, while the Projects platform supports project-based and case-based learning activities. Together with Zenodo and the wider PATTERN platform, these tools strengthen the accessibility, reuse potential and sustainability of the training materials. The Train-the-Trainer approach further supports scalability by enabling trainers, thematic leaders and institutions to adapt and redeliver the materials in different national, disciplinary and organisational contexts. Overall, D2.2 demonstrates that PATTERN has developed a mature and future-oriented curriculum for Open Science and Responsible Research and

Innovation. The curriculum is designed to remain adaptable to evolving European policy priorities, institutional needs and researcher development frameworks. It also provides a basis for continued improvement through monitoring, evaluation and learning, and for continued collaboration across institutions, disciplines and training communities. In this way, the PATTERN curriculum contributes to building an inclusive, fair, open and sustainable research ecosystem by equipping researchers and research support actors with the competences needed to practice and promote responsible research.

Annex I: Thematic Overview of PATTERN Curriculum

THEMATIC AREA	No. OF COURSES (or MODULES)	LEAD PARTNER(S)	LEARNING LEVELS	TOTAL HOURS (est.)	DELIVERY FORMATS	REPRESENTATIVE COURSES (or MODULES)
Open Access	8	UMinho	Beginner	8.5	Asynchronous for training delivery/ Trainer's Guide; Asynchronous; Asynchronous, self paced course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Open Access publishing: overcoming the challenges and busting the myths</i>(Translated into 5 different languages and separate self –pasted courses – Turkish, Portuguese, Greek, Hungarian, Croatian)<i>Empowering Researchers: Retaining Copyright and Maximizing Your Impact in Open Access Publishing</i>(Trainer's Guide) • <i>Meeting Funder Requirements: Navigating Open Access Publishing</i> (Trainer's Guide) • <i>Trusted publishers for my research: decoding good practices & overcoming predatory publishers</i> (Trainer's Guide)
FAIR Research Data Management	5	DANS	Beginner; Intermediate	12	Asynchronous, self paced course; Synchronous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>FAIR Research Data Management: A Practical Introduction</i> (self-paced course for beginners) - translated into separate courses in Hungarian, Greek and Croatian • <i>FAIR Research Data Management: A deeper dive into putting FAIR RDM into practice</i> (self paced course for intermediates) translated into separate courses in Hungarian, Greek and Croatian • <i>State-of-the-Art training in FAIR Research Data Management</i> (Trainer's Guide)

Citizen Science	2	AU	Beginner, intermediate	5	Asynchronous, self-paced course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Introducing Citizen Science: Fundamental principles and interactive cases</i> • <i>Participant Recruitment and Community Engagement</i> • <i>Introducing Citizen Science: Fundamental principles and interactive cases for trainers (Trainer's Guide)</i>
Research Integrity	1	AU EARMA	Beginner	1	Asynchronous, self paced course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Research Integrity & Good Scientific Practice (GSP):</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Good scientific practice: Authorship; Examination of authorship responsibilities, ethical publishing practices, and peer review dilemmas.</i> - <i>Good Scientific Practice and Misconduct: Exploration of GSP, questionable research practices (QRPs), and misconduct such as fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism.</i> - <i>Introduction to research integrity and the virtue-based approach: Overview of research ethics, integrity principles, and virtue-based approaches.</i> - <i>How to foster a responsible research environment? Insights into fostering inclusive, ethical, and collaborative research settings.</i> - <i>Supervision and Mentoring: Understanding roles, responsibilities, and effective mentoring to prevent misconduct and promote integrity.</i>
Gender, Non-discrimination & Inclusion	14	ESF LPI UniSR	Advanced; all	20.5	Asynchronous, self paced course; all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Gender Equality and Inclusion in the Research Lifecycle</i> • <i>A Social-Cognitive Perspective on Gender Bias</i> • <i>Blocking Toxic Speech Online</i>

						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>PBL Workshop: Master suppression techniques, Counter strategies and Confirmation techniques</i> • <i>Risks of informal relationships in the workplace</i> • <i>Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Open Science, Education and Tech</i> • <i>CARE and FAIRness in Power Systems: Collectivist and activist approaches, and an introduction to indigenous feminist epistemologies in Abya Ayala</i> • <i>How to work with Local Communities</i>How to work with ourselves (body and mind) and with inner-power systems. • <i>Em-body-ment and CARE principles: between Interdisciplinary Research and Research Creation</i> • <i>Gender, Diversity and Inclusion in Planetary Health: Foundations of Transformative Research and Inclusive Research Methods</i> • <i>Gender, Diversity and Inclusion in Planetary Health: Participatory Research and FAIR & CARE Data Management</i> • <i>Gender, Diversity and Inclusion in Planetary Health: Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL)</i>
Science Communication	2	SISSA	all	10-12	Asynchronous, self paced course; Asynchronous, Trainer's Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Introduction to Science Communication: Skills for Today's Researchers</i> • <i>Science Communication for Trainers: Tools and Guidelines for Delivery</i>
Mental Health & Leadership	2	SCI LINK	all	2	Asynchronous – Trainer's	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Mental Wellbeing in Academia: The Role of Research Managers_Trainer's Guide:</i> - <i>Choosing and managing your PhD Supervisor</i>

					Guide & PBL Study Cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Breaking the silence around well-being at work</i> - <i>Researcher mental health: advocating for institutional and policy change</i> - <i>Phd careers: how to build transferable skills & address career insecurity</i> - <i>Thriving/surviving as an international postdoctoral researcher</i> - <i>Feedback Workshop for Research Managers on Mental Wellbeing Support in European Institutions</i>
Dissemination & Exploitation	2	APRE LOBA	all	4.5	Asynchronous, self paced course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Get Funding for your Research, then Disseminate, Communicate and Exploit the Results</i> • <i>Enhance your research results, unlock their full potential, enable tangible changes and benefits</i>

PATTERN.

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Research and Innovation

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info@pattern-openresearch.eu